

SHIELD

D4.2. - SHIELD DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

WP 4

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PROJECT PARTNERS

PARTNER NO.	PARTNER ORGANIZATION NAME	COUNTRY	SHORT NAME
1 (PC)	HI-IBERIA INGENIERIA Y PROYECTOS SL	ES	HIB
2	SERVICIO MADRILEÑO DE SALUD	ES	SERMAS
3	UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID	ES	UPM
4	CONSORZIO PER LA RICERCA NELL' AUTOMATICA E NELLE TELECOMUNICAZIONI C.R.A.T	IT	CRAT
5	UNIVERSITY OF LIMERICK	IE	UL
6	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI BARI ALDO MORO BARI IT UNIBA	IT	UNIBA
7	QUALIVE SRL	IT	QUALIVE
8	UNIVERSITE DE GENEVE	CH	UNIGE

LIST OF ACRONYMS

ACRONYM	DEFINITION
NCD	Non-communicable Disease
CVD	Cardiovascular Disease
HF	Heart Failure
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
CDM	Common Data Model
FHIR	Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources
SES	Socio Economic Status
OMOP	Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership
EHR	Electronic Health Records
MLWHFQ	Minnesota living with heart failure questionnaire
GPDR	General Data Protection Regulation
DPA	Data Processing Agreement
DPIA	Data Protection Impact Assessment
DPO	Data Protection Officer
RECs	Research Ethics Committees
IPS	Information Patient Sheet
EEAB	External Ethics Advisory Board
CCER	Commission Cantonale d'Éthique de la Recherche
LLM	Large Language Model

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

In accordance with the Open Science Practices requirements of the Horizon Europe (Grant Agreement No. 101156751 – SHIELD, 2024), this deliverable presents the updated version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the SHIELD project, building on the version previously submitted and reflecting the current status of data management activities at this stage of the project. This deliverable, D4.2 – SHIELD Data Management Plan, provides an updated description of the types of data collected and planned throughout the project and further elaborates on the principles guiding data reuse, access, preservation, and curation strategies.

Aligned with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) for data stewardship under Horizon Europe, and in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (GDPR), an initial inventory of datasets intended for collection and sharing within the SHIELD consortium has been compiled (public, retrospective and prospective), including relevant metadata and context for each dataset.

The main objective of SHIELD is to leverage multimodal data collection, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and collaboration among all actors in the healthcare system to develop risk scores and identify personalized prevention strategies to be tested and validated for two NCDs: cardiovascular disease (CVD) and diabetes, 2 of the 5 major NCDs. These datasets will be integrated into the SHIELD platform, which aims to support open, harmonized, and federated access to data across different institutions for training AI models.

This updated version of the DMP reflects the current status of the project, including the evolution of WP6 activities and the achievement of MS3 on retrospective dataset deployment. Accordingly, the datasets described here reflect the current status of data collection, availability, and planning at this stage of the project. Continuous monitoring will be implemented to ensure that data practices remain aligned with the project's principles throughout the duration of SHIELD. The core guidelines presented here are expected to remain consistent throughout the project lifecycle.

Table of Contents

DOCUMENT HISTORY	2
PROJECT PARTNERS	3
LIST OF ACRONYMS	4
EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	5
LIST OF TABLES	8
1.- Introduction	10
1.1. Purpose of the document	10
1.2. Alignment with the FAIR principles	11
1.3. Involved institutions and roles	11
1.3.1.- Involved Institutions	11
1.3.2.- DMP Roles	12
1.4. Structure of the document	18
2. Data description	19
2.1. Sources, types, and formats of data	19
2.1.1.- Retrospective Data.....	20
2.1.2.- Prospective Data	29
2.1.3.- User-generated data via the SHIELD mobile application	35
2.1.4.- Public datasets available for the project.....	35
2.2. Data collection and consolidation procedures	42
2.2.1. Retrospective clinical data	42
2.2.2. Prospective clinical data.....	42
2.2.3. App- and questionnaire-generated data.....	42
2.2.4. Wearable and device data	43
2.2.5. Data integration and consolidation.....	43
2.3. Standards and metadata	43
2.3.1.- Terminology Standards	43
2.3.2.- SHIELD Terminologies	54

3. Privacy, Ethics, and Legal Compliance	55
3.1. Anonymization and patient identity protection	57
3.2. Compliance with regulations.....	58
3.3. Informed consent and patient rights	60
4. Data security and storage	62
4.1 Storage infrastructure and backup strategies	62
4.2 Data access control and encryption protocols.....	63
4.3 Monitoring, auditing, and recovery plans	63
5. Interoperability, Reusability, and Data Preservation	65
5.1 Interoperability	65
5.2 Reusability	65
5.3 Data preservation.....	66
6. Conclusions and future work.....	67
6.1.- Future Work.....	67
6.2.- Rubric for assessment of the SHIELD DMP.....	67
7. References	79
8. Annexes	81
a) Clinical Questionnaire about data	81
B) Informed consent for User-Generated Data via the SHIELD Mobile Application	94
C) Internal dataset intake status by site and study component	99
Source dataset summary	99
OMOP loading and technical status.....	99

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Summary of roles and responsibilities on SHIELD.....	17
Table 2: Context and variable to be checked on the public datasets.....	19
Table 3: Context and variables from the retrospective data.....	20
Table 4: Overview of Retrospective Data Available from SERMAS.....	22
Table 5: Summary of Retrospective Data Available from SERMAS	24
Table 6: Overview of Retrospective Data Available from UNIBA	25
Table 7: Summary of Retrospective Data Available from UNIBA	27
Table 8: Overview of Retrospective Data Available from UNIGE	27
Table 9: Summary of Retrospective Data Available from UNIGE	29
Table 10. Context and variables from the prospective data.....	29
Table 11: Summary of Prospective Data Available from SERMAS.....	32
Table 12: Summary of Prospective Data Available from UNIBA.....	33
Table 13: Summary of Prospective Data Available from UNIGE.....	34
Table 14: Variables coverage from SHARE	36
Table 15: Variables coverage from ELSA	36
Table 16: Variables coverage from CORE Study	37
Table 17: Variables coverage from 2003 Diabetes	37
Table 18 Variables coverage from Rand Longitudinal	37
Table 19: Variables coverage from Synthea	38
Table 20: Variables coverage from DE SynPUF.....	38
Table 21: Variables coverage from ‘The Coherent Data Set’.....	38
Table 22: Variables coverage from Myocardial infarction complications	39
Table 23: Variables coverage from CDC Diabetes	39
Table 24: Variables coverage from Heart Failure Clinical Records.....	40
Table 25: Variables coverage from Statlog - Heart.....	40
Table 26: Variables coverage from Heart Disease - FLAMBY.....	40
Table 27: Variables coverage from MIMIC IV - Physionet	41
Table 28: Variables coverage from MIMIC III - Physionet	41

Table 29: Variables coverage from EICU - Physionet.....	42
Table 30: SHIELD rubric for Data Management Plan	68
Table 31: Source dataset summary	99
Table 32: OMOP intake and mapping summary.....	99

1.- INTRODUCTION

1.1. PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document, D4.2 – SHIELD Data Management Plan (DMP), constitutes the updated version of the data management strategy for the SHIELD project (Grant Agreement No. 101156751), following the version previously submitted earlier in the project. It has been prepared in accordance with the Open Science Practices requirements of the Horizon Europe programme.

The primary objective of this DMP is to provide preliminary information on the types of data to be collected throughout the project duration and to detail the principles that will guide their management. This includes outlining strategies for reuse, access, preservation, and curation of the data. The document aims to define responsibilities regarding the capture, sharing, use, and preservation of data and associated metadata.

The DMP is aligned with the FAIR principles [1]: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable. FAIR actions aim to enhance the accessibility and reusability of research outputs. It is established that research data and results will be made "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" to ensure both reuse and privacy.

This document describes the origin of the datasets and outlines the data collection and consolidation procedures, including how the data will be gathered, the tools to be used, and the process for integrating data from multiple institutions. It also addresses the preferred medical terminology standards used to harmonize and standardize the data, ensuring semantic interoperability (e.g., ICD-10, ICD 11, SNOMED-CT, ATC, LOINC, among others).

The DMP also covers key aspects of privacy, ethics, and legal compliance. It details adherence to regulations such as the GDPR (EU 2016/679) and applicable national laws. It explains how informed consent will be obtained and managed, the need to anonymize or pseudonymize sensitive data to protect patient privacy, and how patient identity protection will be ensured. In addition, it will guide the ethics-by-design evaluation of the AI systems that will be designed and implemented in SHIELD.

Furthermore, the document addresses data security and storage, including the storage infrastructure (e.g., a CDM implementing OMOP on PostgreSQL), backup strategies, access control, encryption protocols, and monitoring, auditing, and recovery plans.

The institutions involved in defining the DMP include UPM as the lead author, and HI-IBERIA and UNIGE as reviewers. The sections on data description, privacy, ethics, and legal compliance are the responsibility of SERMAS, UNIGE, and UNIBA as clinical partners. Sections on security, storage, interoperability, reuse, and preservation are led by UPM. Specific roles for the DMP are defined in Section 1.3.2 and include legal and governance roles, operational data-management roles, and technical/scientific roles. These roles cover data collection, data controllership and processing, stewardship, analysis, technical integration, and project-level coordination.

Within the broader context of the SHIELD project, which aims to reduce premature mortality from Non-Communicable Diseases (NCDs) such as cardiovascular disease (CVD) and diabetes through personalized prevention and the use of AI on multimodal data, this DMP plays a fundamental role. It ensures that the management of collected data (both retrospective and prospective, including biophysiological, behavioral, psychosocial, and clinical variables), as well as additional public datasets, is conducted in a structured, ethical, and secure manner in compliance with relevant regulations, laying the foundation for the development and validation of the project's risk and intervention tools.

1.2. ALIGNMENT WITH THE FAIR PRINCIPLES

This DMP aligns with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable), in line with the Open Science requirements of Horizon Europe [2] (Grant Agreement No. 101156751 – SHIELD). FAIR principles aim to enhance the reusability of research data by making them more accessible to both humans and machines. In SHIELD, data is managed under the policy of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary,” balancing reusability with privacy protection.

To ensure Findability, SHIELD will store and curate rich metadata (and, where applicable, anonymized derivatives) in the project repository to support discovery and reuse. Clinical personal data will not be centrally stored; it will be retained locally at each site, with federated learning enabling model training without raw data transfers. A consistent file naming convention will be applied, including details like date, project name, work package, task, and version number. Metadata will indicate access rights and support data discovery and reuse.

Accessibility is essential, particularly for retrospective and prospective clinical data. Digital datasets will be made available to authorized consortium members. Retrospective data will remain locally stored at clinical sites. Through a federated learning architecture, hospitals will retain data control while enabling remote access for model training. A Common Data Model (CDM) and a semantic harmonization layer will standardize heterogeneous data. Robust anonymization and pseudonymization protocols and encrypted transfers will safeguard data privacy. Standard data formats (e.g., .csv, json, sql, xml) will be used for both internal exchange and, where possible, public sharing.

Interoperability will be achieved through a CDM based on OMOP[3], and semantic alignment via HL7[4] FHIR[5]. Standard medical terminologies such as ICD (ICD-10, ICD-11), SNOMED-CT, ATC, HPO, and LOINC will ensure consistent clinical, behavioral, and psychosocial data coding across sources.

Regarding technological outputs and models, SHIELD adheres to Open Science principles by promoting immediate open access to research results—software, models, and workflows—where feasible and as defined in the DMP. Public deliverables, scientific outputs, and shareable datasets will be preserved in open-access repositories, supporting clinical, research, and policy use. Explainability of AI models (T7.4) will be prioritized to build user trust and ensure transparent risk stratification and recommendations.

1.3. INVOLVED INSTITUTIONS AND ROLES

1.3.1.- INVOLVED INSTITUTIONS

This section identifies the institutions directly involved in data management within the SHIELD project, as outlined throughout this Data Management Plan (DMP). The main institutions and their roles are:

- **UNIVERSIDAD POLITÉCNICA DE MADRID (UPM)**, Spain: As a technical university, UPM is a core technical partner in SHIELD. It is the author of this DMP (D4.2) and responsible for defining and managing the data infrastructure, technical processes, integration, and security.
- **HI-IBERIA INGENIERIA Y PROYECTOS SL (HIB)**, Spain: As an SME and SHIELD’s project coordinator, HI-IBERIA oversees overall data management and contributes to the review of this DMP (D4.2).
- **Clinical Partners**: These institutions are responsible for collecting participant data at pilot sites in their respective countries and ensuring local ethical and legal compliance. They contribute site-specific regulatory and data-related information for this DMP:
 - **SERVICIO MADRILEÑO DE SALUD (SERMAS)**, Spain – University hospital collecting data in Spain.

- **UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI BARI ALDO MORO (UNIBA)**, Italy – University hospital collecting data in Italy.
- **UNIVERSITÉ DE GENÈVE (UNIGE)**, Switzerland – University hospital and associated partner; involved in data collection in Switzerland, and DMP review.

These institutions jointly ensure the implementation of the data management strategy, aligning with FAIR principles and applicable privacy regulations.

1.3.2.- DMP ROLES

This section defines the roles involved in data management in SHIELD. For clarity, the framework distinguishes between legal and governance roles, operational data-management roles, and technical/scientific roles. Legal and governance roles relate to responsibility for personal data processing, compliance, and oversight, including the Data Controller, the Data Processor, and the relevant institutional data protection supervision function. Operational roles describe how the DMP is implemented across the data lifecycle, including data collection, stewardship, documentation, quality control, access management, and reuse. Technical and scientific roles support data integration, secure storage, interoperability, and analysis. Formal governance processes such as Data Processing Agreements (DPAs) and Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) apply where required. Legal and governance roles define accountability for personal data processing, whereas operational and technical roles describe how data management and processing activities are carried out in practice within the project. A partner may perform more than one operational or technical role. The assignment of these roles in this DMP does not change the legal qualification of any participating entity for data protection purposes.

Research Ethics Committees (RECs) provide ethical oversight at site level, including approval of study protocols and relevant amendments, in line with the applicable national and institutional requirements

DATA CONTROLLER

The Data Controller is the entity that determines the purposes and means of the processing of personal data within the SHIELD project at each clinical site. In SHIELD, the participating clinical institutions acting through their corresponding legally designated entities are responsible for the personal and health data collected in their respective sites.

Objectives:

- Ensure that personal data is processed lawfully, fairly, and transparently.
- Define the purposes of processing and ensure data minimization, proportionality, and storage limitations.
- Protect data subjects' rights and ensure that processing is carried out under the applicable legal and ethical framework.
- Ensure that data shared or further processed within the project are anonymised or pseudonymised where appropriate, in accordance with the intended use, applicable safeguards, and regulatory requirements.

Tasks:

- Authorize and supervise personal data processing activities under their responsibility.
- Maintain the relevant records of processing activities.
- Ensure that legal, ethical, and organizational safeguards are in place before processing starts.
- Designate the relevant institutional contact point for data protection supervision.

- Approve, where required, data access, transfers, and processing arrangements involving third parties or technical partners.
- Define and supervise the conditions under which data are anonymised or pseudonymised before being shared, transferred, or processed within the project.
- Ensure that direct identifiers are removed or replaced where required, and that any re-identification keys or linkage information remain under controlled conditions and restricted access.
- Carry out, where required under Article 35 GDPR and prior to the relevant processing activities, the Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) corresponding to the processing operations under their responsibility, and in accordance with the GDPR, national regulation, ethical requirements, and relevant EDPB guidelines.
- Ensure involvement of the designated Data Protection Officer (DPO), or equivalent institutional data protection supervision function where applicable, in matters relating to personal data processing, including compliance review, DPIAs, and data protection-related decisions.

The Data Controller retains legal responsibility for personal data under its custody, including clinical data, informed consent management, ethics compliance, participant protection, and, where required, the involvement of the designated DPO in accordance with the applicable legal and institutional framework.

DATA PROTECTION OFFICER (DPO)

Where required under the applicable legal and institutional framework, each relevant institution shall rely on its designated Data Protection Officer (DPO), or equivalent institutional data protection supervision function, to support compliance with data protection obligations related to SHIELD processing activities. The DPO shall be involved, properly and in a timely manner, in issues relating to the protection of personal data, in accordance with the applicable data protection framework.

Objectives:

- Support compliance with data protection obligations applicable to the relevant processing activities.
- Advise on the protection of personal data and the safeguards to be applied in the project context.
- Support accountability and oversight in relation to high-risk processing operations, including DPIAs where applicable.

Tasks:

- Inform and advise the relevant institution and its staff on data protection compliance requirements.
- Monitor compliance with the applicable data protection framework and internal policies.
- Provide advice, where required, on Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs).
- Act as a contact point for the competent data protection authority.
- Act, where applicable, as a contact point for data subjects on matters related to personal data protection.

The DPO acts in an advisory and oversight capacity and does not replace the legal responsibility of the Data Controller for the processing operations under its responsibility. The DPO should be able to perform these tasks independently, in accordance with the applicable legal and institutional framework.

DATA COLLECTOR

The Data Collector is responsible for collecting raw data from approved sources such as Electronic Health Records, clinical systems, laboratories, registries, questionnaires, or other study sources. This role ensures that

data are gathered accurately, consistently, and in accordance with the approved study protocol and ethical requirements. In SHIELD, this role is performed by the clinical partners at site level.

Objectives:

- Ensure data quality at the point of collection.
- Adhere to ethical and legal requirements, including informed consent where applicable.
- Document collection procedures to support traceability and reproducibility.

Tasks:

- Collect data from approved clinical and research sources.
- Verify that participant inclusion, consent, and data collection conditions are properly documented.
- Apply initial quality control measures before data are prepared for subsequent processing.
- Ensure traceability of the origin and context of collected data.

DATA PROCESSOR

The Data Processor is responsible for carrying out specific data processing activities on behalf of the Data Controller, only within the scope authorized by the controller and in accordance with the applicable contractual and regulatory framework. In SHIELD, the designated Data Processors are UPM, QUALIVE, HIB and CRAT, acting within their respective technical responsibilities related to data transformation, harmonization, infrastructure, and platform-related processing. This replaces the broader formulation currently used in D4.2, where processor responsibilities are spread across clinical and technical partners.

Objectives:

- Process data only under documented instructions from the corresponding Data Controller.
- Implement appropriate technical and organizational measures to ensure security, confidentiality, integrity, and controlled access.
- Support data harmonization, interoperability, and preparation for approved project purposes.

Tasks:

- Transform, structure, harmonize, and technically prepare data according to project specifications.
- Apply the relevant privacy and security measures required for the authorized processing operations.
- Support the integration of data into the agreed technical environment, including federated or interoperable infrastructures where applicable.
- Assist the Data Controller in demonstrating compliance with security and accountability obligations, where required.

Data Processors should not determine the purposes of processing and shall not engage sub-processors without prior authorization where such authorization is required.

DATA PROCESSING AGREEMENTS (DPAS)

Whenever a Data Processor carries out processing activities on behalf of a Data Controller, such processing shall be governed by a Data Processing Agreement (DPA) or an equivalent binding legal act before the relevant processing activity starts. D5.2 explicitly frames this as a mandatory requirement under Article 28 GDPR.

The DPA will define, at a minimum:

- the subject matter, duration, nature, and purpose of the processing
- the categories of data and data subjects concerned
- the responsibilities and obligations of the Data Controller and the Data Processor
- the obligation of the processor to act only on documented instructions
- confidentiality obligations for authorized personnel
- the technical and organizational measures implemented to protect data
- the conditions for engaging sub-processors, where applicable
- support for data subjects' rights, incident handling, audits, and return, deletion, or secure disposal of data after completion of the processing activity.

The existence of a DPA is required whenever personal data processing is performed by a processor on behalf of a controller.

DATA PROTECTION IMPACT ASSESSMENTS (DPIAS)

Given the nature of SHIELD, including the processing of sensitive health data and the use of AI-based tools in a clinical and research context, Data Protection Impact Assessments (DPIAs) shall be conducted whenever the relevant processing activities are likely to result in a high risk to the rights and freedoms of natural persons. D5.2 specifies that each Data Controller is responsible for its own DPIA and that processors must assist as needed.

Objectives:

- Identify and assess risks associated with the planned processing operations.
- Ensure that appropriate safeguards and mitigation measures are defined before processing begins.
- Support accountability, transparency, and privacy by design across the project.

Tasks:

- Assess the nature, scope, context, and purposes of the relevant processing activities.
- Identify risks related to confidentiality breaches, unauthorized access, re-identification, bias, or misuse of data.
- Define and document technical and organizational safeguards to mitigate such risks.
- Review and update the DPIA when substantial changes occur in data flows, technologies, processing purposes, or risk levels.
- Ensure coordination between the Data Controller and the relevant Data Processors for the information needed to complete the DPIA.

Each Data Controller is responsible for the DPIA corresponding to the processing operations under its responsibility, while the relevant Data Processors shall provide the information and assistance necessary to support such assessments.

DATA STEWARD

The Data Steward is responsible for ensuring the quality, consistency, documentation, traceability, and FAIR-oriented management of the data throughout its lifecycle. In the current D4.2, this role is already assigned across UPM, HIB and the clinical partners, and it makes sense to keep it as an operational role.

Objectives:

- Maintain data quality and consistency over time.

- Ensure appropriate metadata, documentation, and traceability.
- Support secure and governed data sharing and reuse within the project

Tasks:

- Maintain metadata and data documentation aligned with FAIR principles.
- Monitor data quality and coordinate the resolution of inconsistencies.
- Support data curation, versioning, and traceability.
- Facilitate secure and governed data exchange between authorized partners.

This role may be shared between technical and clinical partners depending on the dataset and the relevant stage of the data lifecycle.

DATA ANALYST/SCIENTIST

The Data Analyst/Scientist uses processed and authorized data to generate insights, perform analyses, train or evaluate models, and contribute to the scientific and technical outcomes of SHIELD. This role is already included in the current D4.2 and can remain as an operational/scientific role.

Objectives:

- Design and conduct analyses aligned with the scientific goals of SHIELD.
- Ensure reproducibility and methodological traceability.
- Provide feedback to improve data quality, processing, and interpretation.

Tasks:

- Define scientific questions and analytical strategies.
- Analyze data and document the methods, tools, and assumptions used.
- Contribute to model development, validation, and interpretation under the project framework.
- Report limitations, quality issues, and opportunities for improvement in the datasets.

Only data that are properly authorized and made available under the applicable governance conditions may be used for analytical purposes.

IT/DATA INTEGRATION SPECIALIST

The IT/Data Integration Specialist manages the technical infrastructure required to store, integrate, secure, and exchange data across partners. The current D4.2 already assigns this role to UPM.

Objectives:

- Implement secure data infrastructures and integration pipelines.
- Support semantic and technical interoperability across heterogeneous data sources.
- Ensure continuity, backup, monitoring, and recovery capabilities.

Tasks:

- Set up and maintain secure storage and access-control mechanisms.
- Implement and maintain data integration pipelines, APIs, or interoperability services.
- Support encryption, backup, disaster recovery, and technical monitoring procedures.

- Contribute to logging, traceability, and controlled technical access to project resources.

UPM has the expertise to manage infrastructure, tools, and pipelines for data storage, integration, and security, based on 20+ years of participating in many national and international projects .

SCIENTIFIC COORDINATOR

The Scientific Coordinator oversees the coordination of DMP-related activities within the project and supports alignment across partners on data management, governance, and documentation matters. This role focuses on the implementation, review, and update of the DMP throughout the project lifecycle, in coordination with the relevant project partners

Objectives:

- Ensure coordinated implementation of the DMP across the consortium.
- Promote consistency between data management, governance, scientific, ethical, and regulatory requirements.
- Support the review and update of the DMP as the project evolves.

Tasks:

- Coordinate the implementation of the DMP across the consortium.
- Coordinate the definition and review of DMP-related roles and responsibilities.
- Oversee the update of the DMP throughout the project lifecycle.
- Facilitate communication among partners on data management and governance matters.
- Support alignment between project data management activities and the corresponding scientific, ethical, and regulatory requirements

The Scientific Coordinator supports the consistent implementation and maintenance of the DMP across the project, in coordination with the relevant partners.

Table 1: Summary of roles and responsibilities on SHIELD

Role	Role type	Responsible	Responsibilities
Data Controller	Legal / governance	Participating clinical institutions / site sponsors	Determine the purposes and means of personal data processing; ensure lawful processing, participant protection, ethics compliance, and the conditions for anonymisation or pseudonymisation before sharing or further processing.
Data Collector	Operational	UNIBA, UNIGE, SERMAS	Collect raw data from approved clinical and research sources, ensure data quality at collection, and document collection procedures.
Data Processor	Legal / governance	UPM, QUALIVE, CRAT, HIB	Process data on behalf of the Data Controller under documented instructions; support technical preparation, harmonisation, interoperability, and secure processing.
Data Steward	Operational	UPM, HIB, UNIBA, UNIGE, SERMAS	Maintain data quality, metadata, documentation, traceability, and FAIR-oriented management throughout the data lifecycle.

Data Analyst/Scientist	Technical / scientific	Authorized partners	Analyse datasets, document methodologies, and support reproducible scientific outputs.
IT/Data Integration Specialist	Technical	UPM	Manage infrastructure, interoperability, secure storage, data pipelines, backup, and recovery procedures.
Scientific Coordinator	DMP coordination	UPM	Coordinate DMP implementation and updates, align partners, and support project-wide data governance.

1.4. STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

This document is organized to provide a structured overview of how data will be managed throughout its lifecycle. It covers guiding principles, data types, ethical and security aspects, and general management to ensure compliance with project requirements and relevant regulations.

It begins with an Introduction, outlining the document's purpose, its alignment with the FAIR principles—which are essential for data reusability—and identifying the institutions and roles involved in data management.

Subsequent sections provide further details. The Data Description section addresses data sources, types and formats, collection and consolidation procedures, and standards and metadata for organizing information. The Privacy, Ethics, and Legal Compliance section covers anonymization, patient identity protection, GDPR compliance, and the management of informed consent and patient rights. A dedicated section on Data Security and Storage describes the storage infrastructure, backup strategies, and security protocols for handling sensitive data. The document concludes with Conclusions and Future Work, summarizing key points and outlining next steps.

2. DATA DESCRIPTION

The collected data will encompass both lifestyle factors—such as physical activity, dietary habits, and sleep quality (as far as possible according to electronic health records (EHR) —and clinical parameters, including glycometabolic control and cardiovascular risk factors. These data will be retrospectively extracted from the medical records of patients with diabetes, both with and without a history of cardiovascular disease, as well as patients with an established diagnosis of Heart Failure (HF). The primary purpose of this data collection is to train an artificial intelligence (AI) algorithm, which will be integrated into a mobile application and a clinician-facing dashboard.

The AI algorithm will provide personalized recommendations to help patients manage their chronic condition more effectively, aiming to prevent diabetes progression and the onset or worsening of cardiovascular diseases, in particular the progression of HF. Additionally, a 12-month prospective study will be conducted to evaluate the app's effectiveness in promoting lifestyle changes, improving diabetes management, and reducing the incidence of cardiovascular complications, as well as controlling the progression of heart failure.

These data are of paramount importance for improving preventive care and the management of chronic diseases. By leveraging AI-driven insights, the project aims to facilitate early intervention, personalized support, and evidence-based clinical decision-making, ultimately leading to better health outcomes for individuals with diabetes and cardiovascular disease. Most current AI-based systems designed for medical advice are based on just retrospective data coming from a single hospital, or from public databases (with many potential inconsistencies and biases), without a careful prospective, epidemiologically solid, design. The inclusion of the different SHIELD trials, with patients from different geographical sites, will provide our AI tools with a substantial advantage.

The dataset will include demographic and clinical data such as age, sex, diabetes duration, HbA1c levels, blood pressure, and lipid profile. It will also encompass lifestyle data, including self-reported physical activity, dietary intake, and sleep patterns, as well as cardiovascular risk factors, such as the presence of hypertension and a history of cardiovascular events. Additionally, user interaction data from the mobile application, including engagement with recommendations and adherence to suggested lifestyle modifications, will be collected. The data will be available in structured tabular formats, such as CSV and SQL, selected for AI model training. Survey responses and app usage logs will also be recorded, along with longitudinal clinical data collected over a 12-month period for further analysis.

2.1. SOURCES, TYPES, AND FORMATS OF DATA

This section describes the origin of the datasets (e.g., clinical institutions, patient data, lab results) and detail their types (structured, unstructured) and formats (e.g., CSV, JSON, DICOM).

To describe the coverage of each dataset according to the defined variables we have established the following variable sections:

Table 2: Context and variable to be checked on the public datasets

Profile	age, gender, education, family setting, work capacity, diagnoses, treatments, comorbidities, ethnicity/race, income level, geographic location, transportation access, housing type
Biophysiological	weight, height, waist circumference, BMI, blood pressure, heart rate

Behavioral	Smoking, alcohol and/or drug consumption, nutritional habits, physical activity habits, sleep,
Psychosocial	Stress, anxiety and depression, eating disorders, quality of life
Clinical Data	Total cholesterol, LDL, HDL, triglycerides, fasting glucose, HbA1c, CRP, AST, ALT, GGT
CVD specific	Nt-proBNP, Minnesota living with heart failure questionnaire (MLWHFQ)
Diabetes specific	Fat-free mass, fat mass, HOMA-IR, creatinine, treatment history and adherence, historical management targets, behavioral prescription and recommendations

Index of coverage

2.1.1.- Retrospective Data

This data needs to cover the data summarized by the next context situations and clinical variables:

Table 3: Context and variables from the retrospective data

Category	Variable
Profile Variables	Socio-demographics
	Age
	Gender
	Education level
	Family setting
	Work capacity
	Diagnoses
	Treatments
	Comorbidities
	Other
Biophysiological Variables	Weight
	Height
	Waist circumference
	BMI (Body mass index)
	Blood pressure

	Heart rate
	Other
Behavioral	Smoking
	Alcohol consumption
	Nutritional habits
	Physical activity habits (PAFQ)
	Sleep (PSQI)
	Other
Psychosocial	Stress (STRAIN)
	Anxiety and depression (HAD)
	Eating disorders (EDE-Q)
	Quality of Life (SF-36)
	Other
Common Clinical Data	Total cholesterol
	LDL
	HDL
	Triglycerides
	Fasting glucose
	HbA1c
	Echocardiography
	EKG/ECG
	CRP
	AST
	ALT
	GGT
	Failure with/without valve disease
	Other
CVD Clinical Data	Nt-proBNP
	MLWHFQ
	Other
Diabetes Clinical Data	Fat-free mass
	Fat mass

	HOMA-IR (insuline resistance index)
	Creatinine
	Clinical guidelines for type 2 diabetes

SERMAS DATA

Data for the retrospective study will be obtained from the EHR of the Hospital Universitario La Paz de Madrid in Spain (SERMAS). The retrospective study, will be conducted only after prior approval has been obtained from the Clinical Research Ethics Committee (CEIm) of Hospital Universitario La Paz. From SERMAS clinical site, Hospital Universitario La Paz, structured data will be automatically uploaded from the electronic medical record (HCIS). Unstructured data, on the other hand, will be collected manually.

After approval, data extraction will proceed according to the defined inclusion and exclusion criteria and variables of interest. All the necessary steps will be taken to guarantee the security of the information, such as anonymisation and evaluation. Additionally, access to the collected data will be restricted to authorized personnel only, and all data transfers will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access or breaches.

The sample size defined for this study between 500 and 1,000 adult patients (≥ 23 years) with a diagnosis of heart failure according to the criteria of the European Society of Cardiology, who have had at least one hospital admission for HF decompensation at Hospital Universitario La Paz (HULP)

The target data to be extracted are:

Table 4: Overview of Retrospective Data Available from SERMAS

Category	Variable	Have	Comm.
Profile Variables	Socio-demographics	No	
	Age	Yes	
	Gender	Yes	
	Education level	Yes	
	Family setting	Yes	Y/N of conditions
	Work capacity	Yes*	Employment Status
	Diagnoses	Yes	Structural heart disease, congenital heart disease, valvular heart disease, myocardial infarction, coronary heart disease, diabetes mellitus, arterial hypertension
	Treatments	Yes	ACE Inhibitors, ARBs, Beta-blockers, diuretics, aldosterone antagonists, sacubitril-valsartan, SGLT2 Inhibitors, antiplatelet agents, anticoagulants

	Comorbidities	Yes	Thyroid disease, chronic kidney disease, anemia, dyslipidemia, sleep apnea, Diabetes Mellitus, arrhythmias, Arterial Hypertension, Family History of cardiovascular disease, Sleep Apnea
	Other	Yes	"Social support with caregiver (formal or informal),
Biophysiological Variables	Weight	Yes	
	Height	Yes	
	Waist circumference	No	
	BMI (Body mass index)	Yes	
	Blood pressure	No	
	Heart rate	No	
	Other	Yes	
Behavioral	Smoking	Yes	
	Alcohol consumption	Yes	
	Nutritional habits	No	
	Physical activity habits (PAFQ)	No	
	Sleep (PSQI)	No*	
	Other	Yes	Drug abuse
Psychosocial	Stress (STRAIN)	No	Drug consumption beyond smoking and alcohol
	Anxiety and depression (HAD)	No	
	Eating disorders (EDE-Q)	No	
	Quality of Life (SF-36)	No	
	Other	No	
Common Clinical Data	Total cholesterol	Yes	
	LDL	Yes	
	HDL	Yes	
	Triglycerides	Yes	
	Fasting glucose	Yes	
	HbA1c	Yes	

	Echocardiography	No*	Whether it is performed and when. Normal Echo finding
	EKG/ECG	Yes*	Whether it is performed and when. Normal EKG finding
	CRP	No	
	AST	Yes	
	ALT	Yes	
	GGT	Yes	
	Heart Failure with/without valve disease	Yes	
	Other	Yes	FA, Serum iron, Ferritin, Transferrin saturation index, Hemoglobin, urea, eGFR, sodium, potassium, TSH (thyroid), T4 (thyroid), CA-125
CVD Clinical Data	Nt-proBNP	Yes	
	MLWHFQ	No	
	Other	Yes	NYHA classification, LVEF%, Hospitalizations for HF
Diabetes Clinical Data	Fat-free mass	No	
	Fat mass	No	
	HOMA-IR (insuline resistance index)	No	
	Creatinine	Yes	
	Clinical guidelines for type 2 diabetes	No	

Table 5: Summary of Retrospective Data Available from SERMAS

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
90.0%	50.0%	40.0%	0.0%	84.6%	50.0%	20.0%	72.1%

The data collected by SERMAS has very good overall coverage of variables, with 72.1% of the total. However, the coverage of variables relating to behavior and psychological status can be only partially covered. Specifically, behavioral variables are partially covered —only substance use of alcohol and smoking, and no psychosocial variables will be collected at this site. Biophysiological and general clinical data will have complete coverage except for variables specific to diabetes clinical data which will not be collected.

UNIBA DATA

The data for the retrospective study will be retrieved from the EHR Metaclinic (Meteda). In contrast, the data for the prospective study will be collected using the RedCap software platform, ensuring standardized data entry and secure storage. The retrospective data will be used by informatics and AI specialists to develop and refine the Federated Learning algorithm. Clinicians will rely on the prospective study data to enhance the management of diabetes and cardiovascular diseases. Patients will benefit from AI-driven personalized feedback and lifestyle recommendations, which aim to support self-management and prevent disease progression.

Data from questionnaires and electronic health record (Metaclinic) will be collected by the investigators and entered into RedCap after being anonymised, in compliance with data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Additionally, access to the collected data will be restricted to authorized personnel only, and all data transfers will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access or breaches.

Table 6: Overview of Retrospective Data Available from UNIBA

Category	Variable	Have	Comm.
Profile Variables	Socio-demographics	No	
	Age	Yes	
	Gender	Yes	
	Education level	Yes	
	Family setting	Yes	Y/N of conditions
	Work capacity	Yes*	Profession / Retired status
	Diagnoses	Yes	
	Treatments	Yes	HF hospitalizations, pharmacological treatment
	Comorbidities	Yes	
	Other	No	Family History of Obesity / Diabetes /Dyslipidemia / Hypertension / Myocardial Infarction / Stroke /Cancer / Nephropathy / Neuropathy / - Other
Biophysiological Variables	Weight	Yes	
	Height	Yes	
	Waist circumference	Yes	
	BMI (Body mass index)	Yes	
	Blood pressure	Yes*	Diastolic and Systolic blood pressure
	Heart rate	No	
	Other		Weight at 20 and 50 years old, Hip circumference, Ankle-Brachial Index Minimum

Behavioral	Smoking	Yes	Carotid Plaque Right or Left Dimension
	Alcohol consumption	Yes	Carotid Plaque Right or Left Stenosis Percentage
	Nutritional habits	No	
	Physical activity habits (PAFQ)	No	
	Sleep (PSQI)	No	
	Other	No	
Psychosocial	Stress (STRAIN)	No	
	Anxiety and depression (HAD)	No	
	Eating disorders (EDE-Q)	No	
	Quality of Life (SF-36)	No	
	Other	No	
Common Clinical Data	Total cholesterol	Yes	
	LDL	Yes	
	HDL	Yes	
	Triglycerides	Yes	
	Fasting glucose	No	
	HbA1c	Yes	
	Echocardiography	No	
	EKG/ECG	No	
	CRP	No	
	AST	Yes	
	ALT	Yes	
	GGT	Yes	
	Failure with/without valve disease	Yes	
	Other	Yes	
	CVD Clinical Data	Nt-proBNP	No
MLWHFQ		No	Platelets, Thyroid Stimulating Hormone, eGFR, albuminuria
Other		No	
Diabetes Clinical Data	Fat-free mass	No	
	Fat mass	No	

	HOMA-IR (insuline resistance index)	No	
	Creatinine	Yes	
	Clinical guidelines for type 2 diabetes	No	

Table 7: Summary of Retrospective Data Available from UNIBA

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
80.0%	83.3%	40.0%	0.0%	69.2%	0.0%	20.0%	61.4%

Data from UNIBA will only have partial coverage (61.4%), including primarily biophysiological, profile and general clinical data. No psychosocial, or clinical data specific to cardiovascular diseases or diabetes will be collected.

UNIGE DATA

The data for the retrospective study will be collected from the electronic health record from the Geneva University Hospitals (HUG), Switzerland. In a first step, the study procedures will be submitted for the Commission Cantonale d’Ethique de la Recherche sur l’être humain (CCER) for ethics approval. Upon approval from CCER entity, data transfer agreement will be signed with the Data department of HUG. Finally, data will be extracted according to the inclusion criteria and variables of interest. All the required steps will be covered to ensure security of information such as anonymization and restricted access to authorized personnel.

The preliminary sample size defined for this study is estimated to be between 1,000 and 2,000 individuals. The inclusion criteria required individuals to be diagnosed with obesity (BMI>30), with or without Type 2 diabetes melitus, followed by Patient Education Therapy Unit (Geneva University Hospitals), led by Prof. Zoltan Pataky, for at least 5 years. In addition, individuals must be adults aged between 18 and 75 years old. The target data to be extracted is:

Table 8: Overview of Retrospective Data Available from UNIGE

Category	Variable	Have	Comm.
Profile Variables	Socio-demographics	No	
	Age	Yes	
	Gender	Yes	
	Education level	No	
	Family setting	Yes	Y/N of conditions
	Work capacity	No	
	Diagnoses	Yes	DM2 and duration of diabetes, free-text
	Treatments	Yes	Free-text and use of hypertension medication
	Comorbidities	Yes	Free-text
	Other	Yes	Gender identity, free-text of relevant patient history
	Weight	Yes	

Biophysiological Variables	Height	Yes	
	Waist circumference	Yes	
	BMI (Body mass index)	Yes	
	Blood pressure	Yes	
	Heart rate	Yes	
	Other	No	
Behavioral	Smoking	Yes	
	Alcohol consumption	Yes	
	Nutritional habits	Yes*	Consumption of berries/vegetables/fruits, meal patterns, hunger and satiety, dietary follow-up
	Physical activity habits (PAFQ)	Yes*	Daily physical activity, Vigorous activity, Moderate activity, Walking, Sitting, Comfort with activity, Comfort with activity, Motivation, Barriers
	Sleep (PSQI)	Yes*	Sleep duration
	Other	Yes	Drug consumption, screen time
Psychosocial	Stress (STRAIN)	Yes*	Stress, mood, social factors free text
	Anxiety and depression (HAD)	Yes*	Stress, mood, social factors free text
	Eating disorders (EDE-Q)	Yes*	Stress, mood, social factors free text
	Quality of Life (SF-36)	Yes*	Stress, mood, social factors free text
	Other	No	
Common Clinical Data	Total cholesterol	Yes	
	LDL	Yes	
	HDL	Yes	
	Triglycerides	Yes	
	Fasting glucose	Yes	
	HbA1c	Yes	
	ECG	No	
	CRP	No	
	AST	No	
	ALT	Yes	
GGT	Yes		

	Failure with/without valve disease	Yes	
	Other	No	
CVD Clinical Data	Nt-proBNP	Yes	Hemoglobin, white blood cells, red blood cells, platelets, creatinine, eGFR, proteinuria/creatinine ratio, albumin/creatinine ratio
	MLWHFQ	No	
	Other	No	
Diabetes Clinical Data	Fat-free mass	No	
	Fat mass	No	
	HOMA-IR (insuline resistance index)	No	
	Creatinine	No	
	Clinical guidelines for type 2 diabetes	No	
	Other	No	

The frequency of the data collected at the HUG varies and it is expected to have occurred on a minimum of two occasions per year.

Table 9: Summary of Retrospective Data Available from UNIGE

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
70.0%	100.0%	100.0%	100.0%	69.2%	0.0%	0.0%	77.3%

The retrospective data from UNIGE has good coverage, encompassing 77,3% of the total variables. Non-clinical data has almost complete coverage. However, the diabetes-specific variables defined for SHIELD are not collected, and CVD-specific variables are not systematically available. This is consistent with the nature of the retrospective dataset, which is based on general clinical follow-up data from patients with obesity, with or without type 2 diabetes, rather than on a dataset specifically designed to cover the full SHIELD diabetes- or CVD-specific variable set.

2.1.2.- Prospective Data

The following table describes what variables are expected to be collected for the prospective data.

Table 10. Context and variables from the prospective data

Domain	Variable
Demographical / Profile	Age
	Ethnicity
	Sex
	Education level
	Health Literacy

	Family History of CVD
	Occupational Status
	Urban / rural location
	Work capacity
	Composite SES Indices (optional, can be derived from location data)
	Area-level Deprivation Index (optional, can be derived from location data)
	Household Income (optional, can be derived from location data or collected as income brackets)
	Distance to Access Medical Services (optional, can be derived from location data)
	Family Setting
Behavioral	Smoking Status
	Drug & Alcohol Consumption
	Sleep Duration & Disturbance (questionnaire)
	Physical Inactivity Questionnaire
	Wearable Measurement of Physical Activity
	Dietary Intake / Nutritional Habits
	Adherence to Medical Therapy
	App Engagement (system performance metrics)
	Smartphone Usage (questionnaire)
	Long Term App Retention (questionnaire)
	Feature Specific App Usage (system performance metrics)
	Screen Time (system performance metrics)
Psychosocial	Anorexia Nervosa (EDs)
	Binge Eating Disorder (EDs)
	Bulimia Nervosa (EDs)
	Chronic Stress
	Anxiety
	Depression (Sub-clinical)
	Loneliness
	Patient Activation
	Patient Emotions and Subjective Well-being
	Patient Health Chang Motivation and Activation Scale
	Patient Health Self-efficacy
	Health-Related Quality of Life
Diagnoses / Comorbidities / Treatments	Atypical Antipsychotic Use
	Corticosteroid Use
	Hypertension Treatment Status
	Statin Use
	Chronic Kidney Disease
	Diabetes Status (pre-existing)
	Rheumatoid Arthritis
Biophysiological	Weight
	Height

	Body Mass Index
	Waist Circumference
	Respiratory Rate with Wearable
	Oxygen Saturation with Wearable
	Pulse Pressure (not wearable)
	Blood Pressure (wearable) (Systolic, Diastolic)
	Systolic/Diastolic BP (not wearable)
	Heart Rate Variability
	Heart Rate with Wearable
Clinical	Blood Glucose (HbA1c)
	HDL Cholesterol
	LDL Cholesterol
	Non-HDL Cholesterol
	Total:HDL Cholesterol Ratio
	Triglycerides
	ACR (standard)
	Creatinine
	EGFR by EPI-CKD
Log ACR (Albumin:Creatinine Ratio)	
CVD-Specific	Nt-proBNP
	Atrial Fibrillation
	Dyspnea, Leg Edema, etc.
	Heart Failure with/without Valve Disease
	Hospitalizations
	Major Adverse Cardiovascular Events (MACE)
	Systemic Lupus Erythematosus (SLE)
	MLWHF Questionnaire (this should be considered as a specific instrument for HF)
	Clinical Guidelines for T2D and adherence
Diabetes-Specific	Duration of Diabetes
	Age at Diabetes Diagnosis
	Time in Range (TIR) with wearable
	Plasma Glucose with Wearable
Other data that might be derived from location data instead of collecting it in detail	Weather, Traffic, Time Zone, Pollution, access to nature, Area-Level Deprivation Index, Average Household Income

A more detailed operational summary of the datasets received so far, organized by site, study component, and data source, is provided in Annex C) Internal summary of datasets (Internal dataset intake status by site and study component). This annex is intended for internal project use and complements the present description by providing a site-level overview of retrospective and prospective datasets, including their availability and current intake status.

SERMAS DATA

SHIELD is a randomized, cluster-controlled, clinical trial comparing standard of care versus personalized SHIELD AI-based recommendations. The final sample of prospective clinical study to be conducted at SERMAS is under discussion. It is calculated an estimation number of 200 participants per site, subject to final sample size calculation. Patients will be recruited in the Hospital Universitario La Paz within the context of the SHIELD trial, which is planned in two phases. Each patient recruited will be follow up during 6 months at each phase, and the total duration of the prospective study is almost two years of duration. . The study will take place at Hospital La Paz in Madrid (Spain), and participants will be followed for a fixed period of 6 months, although the final follow-up duration is still under discussion. The study protocol will be submitted to the Research Ethics Committee and, where applicable, to the competent national authorities for approval. The study will be conducted in accordance with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki (1996), the International Conference on Harmonization of Good Clinical Practice, and local, national, and international regulations, including legal regulations on personal data confidentiality (Organic Law 3/2018, of 5 December, on the Protection of Personal Data and guarantee of digital rights, and Regulation [EU] 2016/679, General Data Protection Regulation). All enrolled patients will provide written informed consent to participate in the study.

The main eligibility inclusion and exclusion criteria are under discussion. Participants will be allocated and randomized in different study arms, which are the Control Group, the SHIELD Intervention Group 1, with no system personalization, and the SHIELD Intervention Group 2 with the personalization system. The expected randomization ratio could be 2:1, pending for the final trial design definition. Randomization will be stratified. The stratification criteria and the risk score model used are under discussion.

The data collected will follow the list described in Table 10, with some exceptions:

- Variables that will not be collected: Clinical Guideline Adherence for T2D, Eating Disorders, Continuous Blood Glucose Monitorization, Time in Range, and the optional demographic variables.
- Variables outside the list that may be collected: New York Heart Association Functional Classification (NYHA), Sodium, Potassium, Left Ventricular Ejection Fraction, Hydric Balance, Diuresis, C-Reactive Protein/Inflammatory Index, AST, ALT, GGT, ECG/EKG normal findings Body temperature (only in case the wearables/smartwatch provide this data), Quality of Life in patients with HF by the MLHFQ quesitonnaire, Sleep/Wake Cycles with wearables, and HF related mortality.

Table 11: Summary of Prospective Data Available from SERMAS

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	40%	92.41%

SERMAS shows high coverage of all data, except for psychosocial (attributed to not recording eating disorders), and diabetes-specific data, which lacks the collection of clinical guidelines adherence for T2D, and continuous glucose sensor data.

UNIBA DATA

The prospective clinical study that will be performed at UNIBA will include data from questionnaires and Electronic Health Records, extracted from Metaclinic Information System. Data will be collected by the investigators and entered into RedCap after being pseudonymized, in compliance with data protection regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR).

Additionally, access to the collected data will be restricted to authorized personnel only, and all data transfers will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access or breaches.

The data collected will include all the variables defined in Table 10 with minor alterations:

- a. A subset of patients will have continuous monitoring devices. This restricts the availability of measures such as continuous plasma glucose measurement, oxygen saturation, physical activity (steps, distance, etc.), heart rate, or respiration rate.
- b. Variables that will not be collected: Eating Disorders,
- c. Variables outside the list that may be collected: Polycystic Ovary Syndrome, Gestational Diabetes, Erectile Dysfunction, Retinopathy, Social Isolation, Hostility/Anger, Subjective Social Status, Wealth, ECG/EKG, Detailed sleep architecture, Migraine, Distance to access medical services, AST, ALT, GGT, MACE, NYHA, Creatinine, eGFR, Dyspnea, Leg edema, Weather, Patient Stress, Body Temperature, Sleep/wake cycles, Diabetes Distress, Diabetes Related Hospitalizations, and Mortality.

Table 12: Summary of Prospective Data Available from UNIBA

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
100%	100%	100%	75%	100%	100%	100%	96.2%

UNIBA has very high coverage of all data, except for psychosocial (attributed to not recording eating disorders). However, while the coverage of continuous variables from wearables is complete, the amount of data collected may be lower due to only a subset of patients having continuous monitoring devices.

UNIGE DATA

The prospective clinical study that will be performed at UNIGE aims to recruit a cohort of 400 participants with T2DM or obesity (BMI>30). A final general sample size is going to be calculated. A 3-arm randomized controlled trial study design will be constituted by a control group, an intervention group using v1.0 of the SHIELD app (general intervention based on risk stratification), and an intervention group using v2.0 of the SHIELD app (personalized intervention). The recruitment will be done sequentially in blocks with a randomized allocation of control group of 2:1. In addition, data collection will be done during two phases. During Phase I, which will last 12 months, the patients allocated to intervention will use the SHIELD v1.0 for 6 months. Afterwards, during the Phase II, similarly, the patients allocated to intervention will use the SHIELD v2.0 for 6 months. The active control group will receive no intervention during participation in the study. Recruitment will be mainly done by the Patient Education Therapy Unit (Geneva University Hospitals), led by Prof. Zoltan Pataky. In addition, complementary recruitment in public areas will be used. Baseline and follow-up clinical measurements will be collected at Day 1, and at three and six months, during clinical consultation for all participants.

The duration of the observational phase will be 12 months, in which data will be collected through sporadic questionnaires, clinical follow-up (at 3 and 6 months) and the use of measurement devices (wearables, smart scale, blood pressure monitor).

The data collected will include all the variables defined in Table 10 with minor alterations:

- a. Supplementary variables will be added, such as: Family history of diabetes, obesity, or cancer; SDA and SCORE2 scores; blood analysis variables (white blood cells, red blood cells, platelets, fasting

glucose, proteinuria/creatinine ratio, LDL and LDL-C); physical activation and follow-up questions on comfort, diet, motivation and barriers, detailed sleep architecture and EKGs.

- b. Variables that may not be collected: blood pressure using wearables, time in range, hospitalizations, major adverse cardiovascular events, MLWHFQ, and 'Dyspnea, edema, etc'.

The data collected from wearables will also be synchronized directly from the builder's app to UNIGE data servers. In the first (and only) scheduled visit, participants will be explained about the use of all devices and mobile app. As summarized in the table, four devices will be provided to the participants:

- 1- Smartwatch. (device brand & model to be defined)
 - a. Heart rate (bpm)
 - b. Physical activity levels, typology (e.g. run, cycling, swim), Steps, step length, distance, walking speed, elevation, calories
 - c. Sleep (cycles duration)
 - d. Heart Rate Variability
 - e. Glucose sensor. Abbot FreeStyle Libre ¹
 - f. Continuous glucose levels (sensor lifetime = 14 days)

The inclusion of the glucose sensor will be for a small sub-group of individuals based on the budget. (strategy yet to define)

- 2- Blood pressure monitoring device (device to be defined)

- a. Blood pressure (systolic, diastolic)

- 3- Smart scale.(device to be defined)

- a. Weight

- b. Due to budget limitations, the inclusion of glucose sensors will be centered on a randomly selected sub-group of participants (n=30). They will receive two devices which will allow the measurement of glucose during two intervals of two weeks (maximum capacity of each sensor is 14 days). In parallel, all participants will be asked, upon their acceptance, for their daily glucose measurements of registration. Only patients diagnosed with T2D will be selected to receive the CGM device. During the continuous glucose monitoring window, participants will be asked to collect daily food intake (by either photographs or a written diary). Equally, the inclusion of the blood pressure monitoring device will be carried out on a randomly selected sub-group (n=30, equivalent to 10% of the subject population). Participants will perform measurements at their own will (recommended and expected a minimum of 2 measurements per week). Those two devices will be optional and so if participants do not accept it, his/her participation will still be considered, but we will select another candidate randomly selected, for the integration of the optional devices.

Table 13: Summary of Prospective Data Available from UNIGE

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
100%	91%	100%	75%	100%	50%	80%	96.2%

¹ <https://www.freestyle.abbott/ch-fr/nos-produits/freestyle-libre-3.html>

UNIGE shows a similar pattern of missingness of eating disorder data and wearable data for continuous monitoring of glucose, specifically time-in-range. The CVD-specific variable coverage is much lower, but it is to be expected because UNIGE focuses on diabetes and obesity patients.

2.1.3.- User-generated data via the SHIELD mobile application

In addition to the prospective datasets collected at each clinical site, user-generated data will be captured directly through the SHIELD mobile application. This includes self-reported information via in-app forms and questionnaires (Annex A).

The SHIELD mobile application will serve also as a key data collection point for information generated by wearable devices, complementing the self-reported data gathered through integrated questionnaires and forms. The app is designed to seamlessly integrate with selected wearables, enabling the retrieval of essential biomarkers and lifestyle data from participants. This includes metrics such as physical activity levels, step count, sleep patterns, heart rate, body temperature, and potentially others, depending on the specific device used. All data collected via the application, as part of the project's prospective dataset, will be securely stored within the SHIELD project infrastructure and managed according to the same strict protocols for data retention, pseudonymization/anonymization, and restricted access as those applied to questionnaire data, ensuring full compliance with GDPR and ethical standards.

These instruments will be deployed at regular intervals to gather key longitudinal data, complementing the biophysiological measurements obtained from wearable devices.

Data Management and Retention

All mobile app data will be securely stored within the SHIELD project infrastructure in accordance with participants' informed consent (Annex B). Data will be retained for a planned period of five years. To protect privacy, rigorous anonymization or pseudonymization procedures will be applied before any analysis or sharing.

Subject to ethical approval and the terms of informed consent, anonymized datasets may be shared with external researchers via open-science platforms (e.g., the SHIELD project repository or EOSC), following the guiding principle:

“as open as possible, as closed as necessary.”

A draft version of the in-app data collection form is included as an annex to this document (Annex A). This form has been translated into Spanish, French, and Italian to ensure cultural and linguistic appropriateness for participants in each pilot country. The final version will be incorporated in upcoming revisions of the Data Management Plan (D4.2).

2.1.4.- Public datasets available for the project

In addition to the datasets provided by the clinical partners, the use and integration of publicly available datasets should also be considered. These datasets can complement the project's data landscape and support model training, validation, and benchmarking. Public sources such as:

- SHARE (the Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe),
- ELSA (the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing),
- HRS (Health and Retirement Study)
- FLAmby (Federated Learning Ample Benchmark of Your cross-silo strategies) that proposes a novel cross-silo dataset suite focused on Federated Learning (FL) for healthcare.

- Synthea, the Coherent Data Set.
- MIMIC

Where applicable, and in cases where genetic predisposition to non-communicable diseases (NCDs) is relevant, SHIELD will support data enrichment by enabling links to a wide range of public genetic databases, such as OMIM (for human genes and genetic phenotypes), ORPHANET (for rare diseases), HPO (Human Phenotype Ontology), and others

SHARE

The Survey of Health, Ageing and Retirement in Europe[7] data concerns social and behavioral determinants of health (SBDH) of elderly population. Data is obtained along 9 waves, 2-year separated, of surveys with either several options (Yes, No) or discrete scales (1 to 9), where the user must keep their information up to date.

SHARE has a great coverage of the profile, biophysiological and behavioral variables, in addition to that, it does have questions related to the psychosocial variables. Its main drawback is that it has no data coverage of the clinical data variables specific to both CVD and Diabetes diseases are not covered with any variable.

Table 14: Variables coverage from SHARE

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
77%	76,92%	100%	75%	0%	0%	0%	44,68%

ELSA

At the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing[8] respondents are asked to complete a core self-completion questionnaire covering questions such as wellbeing, relationships and alcohol consumption. The study is divided into 11 waves where health visits are carried out in 6 of them, gathering clinical data from interviewees, including physical examination and performance along with biological samples.

ELSA contains demographic and economic data that aligns with the profile and behavioral variables defined. The physical health and psychosocial measures provide clinical data including biophysiological information as well as blood-based outcomes and liver tests covering most of the specific variables for both CVD and diabetes diseases. Also, psychosocial variables are covered via quantitative questions that approximate to the standardized questionnaires questions.

Table 15: Variables coverage from ELSA

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
77%	76,92%	100%	75%	60%	0%	28,57%	65,96%

HRS

The University of Michigan Health and Retirement Study (HRS)[9] is a longitudinal panel study that surveys a representative sample of approximately 20,000 people in US. Information on the health and economic circumstances of adults over age 50 in the United States. The Health and Retirement Study provide several datasets that relates with the study and that are listed below.

2022 CORE STUDY

This study is divided into 15 waves, two years divided each and contains the main part of the data, its sample size currently ranges from 18-23k any given wave. It covers most of the demographic variables (profile, biophysiological and behavioral). It also includes questions related to the psychosocial questionnaires. On the other hand, it covers the clinical data poorly compared to the other variables only covering blood pressure and historical treatments.

Table 16: Variables coverage from CORE Study

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
85%	84,62%	80%	50%	0%	0%	14,29%	46,81%

2003 DIABETES

Main study conducted in 2003 and 2004 with a sample of people reporting diabetes in the 2002 diabetes core wave. The study was administered in two stages: first, a self-administered questionnaire about diabetes care, self-management, and health care utilization, and second, a mail-in kit with a finger-stick dried blood spot sample to measure levels of hemoglobin A1c. Of the 3,194 respondents who reported a diagnosis of diabetes in the 2002 HRS, 2,381 were eligible to participate in the study after exclusions for death or random assignment to another study. Of these eligible cases, 1,901 returned a questionnaire and 1,233 had valid laboratory data.

This dataset is the smallest one among the 3 HRS datasets. It has worse coverage of the profile, biophysiological and behavioral variables than the Core module but better coverage of the clinical data and diabetes specific variables. On the other hand, it does not cover at all the psychosocial variables.

Table 17: Variables coverage from 2003 Diabetes

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
38%	38,46%	40%	0%	10%	0%	42,86%	27,66%

RAND LONGITUDINAL

It includes cleaned, processed and more intuitive data from all fifteen waves of the core interview data as well as exit interview data. It also contains spousal counterparts of most individual-level variables and model-based imputations.

It is the most complete dataset among the three. It covers most of the demographic variables (profile and behavioral) and has related variables to most of the psychosocial variables. It contains some of the clinical data required covering most of the biophysiological variables, and poorly the CVD and diabetes data. It has less diabetes coverage than the 2003 Diabetes dataset.

Table 18 Variables coverage from Rand Longitudinal

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
77%	76,92%	80%	75%	10%	0%	14,29%	51,06%

SYNTHEA

Synthea[10] is a synthetic patient population simulator. It produces synthetic, realistic patient data and its associated health records in a variety of formats. There are already existing modules for diabetes (metabolic syndrome disease), hypertension, atrial fibrillation, myocardial infarction, stable ischemic heart disease, stroke,

and valvular heart disease (VHD). They simulate patients from birth to death, including doctor appointments all using public statistics and current rule procedures to diagnose things to the fake patients. Considering its flexibility, Synthea can cover all variables defined.

Table 19: Variables coverage from Synthea

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

DE-SYNPUF

Data Entrepreneurs’ Synthetic Public Use File (DE-SynPUF)[11] dataset, created with Synthea, provides realistic synthetic Medicare claims data while protecting beneficiaries' privacy. It supports the development of software and applications for CMS claims data, aids researchers in training, and encourages safe data mining innovations. It includes five data types: Beneficiary Summary, Inpatient Claims, Outpatient Claims, Carrier Claims, and Prescription Drug Events. The dataset is available for the years 2008-2010, with each year providing varying numbers of records. Data is divided into 20 separate samples for easier access, and a unique identifier is used for linking data. This identifier does not contain personal patient information and is used solely for processing.

While DE-SynPUF contains vast amounts of data, its primary focus is on expenses and insurance, rather than on conditions like CVD or Diabetes. The dataset includes very few variables relevant to the study, mainly limited to profile and biophysiological data, with no clinical data included:

Table 20: Variables coverage from DE SynPUF

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
38%	38,46%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	10,64%

THE COHERENT DATASET

The “Coherent Data Set”[12] is a set of synthetic open access data created by The MITRE Corporation to help the development and evaluation of health information exchange systems and interoperability frameworks. They used Synthea and supplemented it with other simulation models like SBML models to generate longitudinal clinical histories worth of EHRs of more than 1000 patients using hundreds of thousands of FHIR resources. It includes genomic data of families of up to three generations, medical imaging (MRIs) in DICOM format, clinical notes in SOAP format, and temporal series of physiological signals like EKGs. The goal of this dataset is to be used to help in the development and evaluation of health information exchange systems and interoperability frameworks.

It covers up to 50% of the desired variables, which is among the highest coverage found among public datasets. However, given that it is synthetic and that it was created using a publicly available tool (Synthea) it is preferable to create another Synthetic dataset with complete coverage of the variables. Because of this and the mixture of data in different formats such as FHIR resources and images, this dataset is not considered relevant for our use case.

Table 21: Variables coverage from ‘The Coherent Data Set’

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
77%	76,92%	20%	0%	80%	50%	42,86%	59,57%

UC IRVINE DATASETS

The UCI[13] Machine Learning Repository is a collection of databases, domain theories, and data generators that are used by the machine learning community. Among the databases available in the repository, we focused on the heart/diabetes related ones:

MYOCARDIAL INFARCTION COMPLICATIONS

The dataset is designed to test and compare data mining and pattern recognition methods using real-life medical complexity. It focuses on predicting complications of Myocardial Infarction (MI)[14] based on patient data at admission and on the third day of hospitalization. It also supports disease phenotyping, dynamic phenotyping, and visualization through clustering and trajectory identification. MI remains a major global health challenge with high incidence and mortality rates, particularly in urban populations of developed countries. The dataset aims to aid in predicting MI complications, as even experienced specialists may struggle to foresee them, enabling timely preventive measures to improve patient outcomes.

While the dataset contains specific data related with MI it does not cover the variables described in the study. It lacks clinical, behavioral, psychosocial and both CVD and Diabetes data.

Table 22: Variables coverage from Myocardial infarction complications

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
38%	38,46%	0%	0%	0%	0%	0%	14,89%

CDC DIABETES HEALTH INDICATORS

The Diabetes Health Indicators Dataset[15] contains healthcare statistics and lifestyle survey information about people in general along with their diagnosis of diabetes. The 35 features consist of some demographics, lab test results, and answers to survey questions for each patient. The target variable for classification is whether a patient has diabetes, is pre-diabetic, or healthy.

As the data is obtained via survey questions most of the variables are binary, which at most guarantees that a variable is covered with a yes or no answer. Despite this, the dataset has good behavioral, profile and biophysiological coverage, lacking clinical and psychosocial data.

Table 23: Variables coverage from CDC Diabetes

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
46%	46,15%	80%	25%	10%	0%	0%	29,79%

HEART FAILURE CLINICAL RECORDS

The dataset[16] contains medical records of 299 heart failure patients collected in Faisalabad, Pakistan, between April and December 2015. The patients, aged 40 to 95, included 105 women and 194 men, all with left ventricular systolic dysfunction and previous heart failures classified as NYHA stage III or IV. The target variable, death event, indicates whether a patient survived or died during an average follow-up period of 130 days. The dataset is imbalanced, with 203 survivors (67.89%) and 96 deceased patients (32.11%). The dataset is structured as a table with 299 rows and 13 columns, with some feature names slightly modified for clarity.

This dataset contains only 13 features, including specific ones like creatinine phosphokinase (CPK), ejection fraction, and serum creatinine. The limited number of variables makes it difficult to achieve the desired coverage, as it lacks clinical and psychosocial data and provides insufficient coverage on other variables.

Table 24: Variables coverage from Heart Failure Clinical Records

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
23%	23,1%	20%	0%	0%	0%	14,3%	12,8%

STATLOG (HEART)

The Statlog[17] dataset is not described in the UC Irvine repository, and it lacks the original paper and author information. Additionally, it provides limited coverage of the study variables due to the small number of available features, covering only a few profile, biophysiological, and clinical data variables.

Table 25: Variables coverage from Statlog - Heart

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
23%	23,1%	0%	0%	10%	0%	0%	12,8%

HEART DISEASE (FLAMBY)

FLamby[18] is a benchmark for cross-silo Federated Learning with natural partitioning, currently focused in healthcare applications. FLamby is a dataset suite instead of a repository. It can be used to access seven different datasets, among them the only interesting for our study is the Fed-Heart Disease dataset from UC Irvine. The Fed-Heart Disease dataset was collected in in four centers: Cleveland, Hungary, Switzerland and Long Beach V.

This dataset covers the profile, behavioral and biophysiological variables poorly compared to the other datasets. In addition to that, it does not cover any psychosocial variable and has poor CVD variables coverage considering that it is a heart disease dataset and does not have great clinical data coverage. All in all, it is not a useful dataset for this study.

Table 26: Variables coverage from Heart Disease - FLAMBY

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
38%	38,46%	40%	0%	20%	0%	0%	23,40%

PHYSIONET DATASETS

PhysioNet is a widely used repository of biomedical data and software that supports reproducible research by providing access to diverse physiological recordings—from early ECG datasets like the MIT-BIH Arrhythmia Database to a variety of time-series clinical signals. Its resources underpin challenges in areas such as arrhythmia detection and sleep apnea identification, promoting innovation in computational physiology. Specifically, the MIMIC III, MIMIC IV], and eICU databases offer detailed hospital data that covers most of the variables described for the retrospective data. These databases are under the PhysioNet Credentialed Health Data License 1.5.0, which requires mainly to only provide access to credentialed users that have requested access, to contribute the code associated with publications to be openly accessible, and for the specific purpose in sent in the request.

MIMIC IV (PHYSIONET)

The MIMIC-IV[20] dataset is a comprehensive, deidentified medical database that includes retrospective data from over 65,000 ICU patients and more than 200,000 emergency department patients at the Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center between 2008 and 2022. It is organized in a modular fashion, consolidating data from both a hospital-wide electronic health record system and an ICU-specific clinical information system. The dataset underwent a rigorous three-step process of acquisition, preparation, and deidentification—including techniques such as denormalization, removal of audit trails, and date shifting—to ensure patient privacy while preserving the clinical time relationships inherent in the raw data. This robust structure facilitates a wide array of research applications, from predictive modeling to retrospective epidemiological studies.

MIMIC-IV has excellent coverage of clinical data with 100% representation and a moderate inclusion of diabetes-related variables (42.9%). In addition, it provides some profile and biophysiological information (46.2% each); however, it lacks any coverage of behavioral, psychosocial, and cardiovascular disease (CVD) variables.

Table 27: Variables coverage from MIMIC IV - Physionet

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
46,2%	46,2%	0%	0%	100%	0%	42,9%	51,1%

MIMIC III (PHYSIONET)

MIMIC-III[19] is a previous version of MIMIC IV. Like its successor, it is a comprehensive and expansive database encompassing detailed clinical data from over forty thousand patients admitted to critical care units at the Beth Israel Deaconess Medical Center between 2001 and 2012. It includes a wide array of information crucial for medical research, such as demographics, hourly vital signs, laboratory results, procedures, medications, caregiver notes, imaging reports, and even post-hospital mortality data. This dataset stands out for its vast coverage of clinical variables, achieving 100% coverage in this domain, making it a pivotal resource for epidemiological studies, clinical decision-rule enhancement, and the development of electronic health tools. Moreover, MIMIC-III is freely accessible globally, facilitating reproducibility and innovation in healthcare research without imposing burdens on caregivers or disrupting hospital workflows.

In terms of other variable domains, MIMIC-III offers moderate coverage of profile and biophysiological variables at 46.2% each. However, it does not include any behavioral or psychosocial variables. Cardiovascular disease CVD-specific data is also not covered, while diabetes-specific information is partially available at 14.3%. Overall, the dataset achieves a total coverage of 46.8%, highlighting its primary strength in clinical data while noting limited support for non-clinical variables.

Table 28: Variables coverage from MIMIC III - Physionet

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
46,2%	46,2%	0,0%	0,0%	100,0%	0,0%	14,3%	46,8%

eICU (PHYSIONET)

The eICU[21] Collaborative Research Database is a multi-center deidentified clinical dataset that compiles health information from over 200,000 ICU admissions across 208 hospitals in the United States during 2014–2015. It includes vital sign measurements, care plan documentation, APACHE severity of illness measures, diagnosis details, and treatment information, all collected via the Philips eICU telehealth system. This comprehensive

collection ensures that key clinical parameters and patient care activities in intensive care settings are well documented and readily available for research.

In terms of variable coverage, the eICU Collaborative Research Database provides strong support for clinical data with an 80.0% coverage. It also includes moderate coverage for profile and biophysiological variables at 46.2% each, while behavioral and psychosocial data are not represented (0.0% coverage). Although there is no coverage for CVD-specific data, the database includes partial information on diabetes-specific data at 28.6%. Overall, the dataset achieves a total coverage of 44.7%, highlighting its primary focus on clinical data while offering limited insights into non-clinical dimensions.

Table 29: Variables coverage from EICU - Physionet

Profile	Biophysiological	Behavioral	Psychosocial	Clinical data	CVD	Diabetes	Total
46,2%	46,2%	0,0%	0,0%	80,0%	0,0%	28,6%	44,7%

2.2. DATA COLLECTION AND CONSOLIDATION PROCEDURES

Data collection and consolidation in SHIELD includes several complementary streams, depending on the origin and purpose of the data. For clarity, these procedures are described below according to the main data sources involved in the project: retrospective clinical data, prospective clinical data, app- and questionnaire-generated data, wearable and device data, and the subsequent integration and consolidation process.

2.2.1. RETROSPECTIVE CLINICAL DATA

Retrospective data are collected from the clinical information systems available at each participating site. These data are extracted from existing Electronic Health Records (EHRs) and other institutional clinical sources, depending on the local infrastructure and data availability. The extraction may include both structured and, where feasible, relevant unstructured information.

These retrospective datasets are used to support the initial development and training of the SHIELD AI models. Before being shared or further processed within the project, the data are prepared at site level in accordance with the applicable legal, ethical, and governance framework, including the use of anonymisation or pseudonymisation where appropriate.

2.2.2. PROSPECTIVE CLINICAL DATA

Prospective clinical data will be generated within the SHIELD clinical study and collected according to the corresponding study procedures at each site. These data may include baseline and follow-up clinical information, laboratory parameters, clinical outcomes, and other study-related variables defined in the protocol.

Where applicable, structured study data will be entered into the corresponding electronic data capture environment used at site level, such as REDCap or the project eCRF platform. The final configuration may vary depending on the site-specific study workflow, and the tools adopted for prospective data capture.

2.2.3. APP- AND QUESTIONNAIRE-GENERATED DATA

Additional prospective data will be collected through the SHIELD mobile application and related digital questionnaires. These data include self-reported information such as lifestyle variables, behavioral factors, psychosocial measures, PREMs/PROMs, and app usage indicators.

Questionnaire-based data may be collected directly through the mobile application or through other approved digital tools integrated into the study workflow. These data streams complement the clinical data by providing patient-reported and digitally generated information relevant to the SHIELD use cases.

2.2.4. WEARABLE AND DEVICE DATA

The project also foresees the collection of selected physiological and behavioral variables through wearable or home-monitoring devices, subject to site-specific implementation and final study procedures. These data may include, for example, physical activity, heart rate, sleep-related measures, blood pressure, oxygen saturation, or other device-generated observations, depending on the devices finally deployed.

Where relevant, these data will be synchronized through the corresponding digital infrastructure and linked to the rest of the study data under controlled conditions and according to the applicable governance framework.

2.2.5. DATA INTEGRATION AND CONSOLIDATION

After data collection, the different data streams will be prepared for integration through a controlled consolidation process. This process may include normalization, harmonization, and the transformation of datasets into the SHIELD common data model where applicable.

The integration process will combine data from multiple institutions and sources, including retrospective clinical data, prospective study data, app- and questionnaire-generated data, wearable/device data, and selected public datasets where relevant. For technical interoperability and downstream analysis, the project will rely on common specifications and harmonization procedures, including the transformation of authorized datasets into the SHIELD common data model based on OMOP.

Only data that have been properly authorized and prepared in accordance with the project's legal, ethical, and technical requirements will be integrated and made available for the corresponding project activities.

2.3. STANDARDS AND METADATA

This section outlines the standards and protocols used to harmonize and structure data (e.g., SNOMED, HL7, FHIR, OMOP, HPO...etc.). Include methods to apply FAIR principles to ensure data consistency and usability. Specify the metadata standards that will be adopted to ensure data discoverability and compliance with FAIR (e.g., Dublin Core, clinical metadata schemas).

2.3.1.- Terminology Standards

There are many medical terminologies used actively depending on the domain and purpose. In this section, the different popular terminologies used in Europe will be explained and an outline of the terminologies that will be used in this project will be discussed. In this chapter, vocabulary, terminology, ontology and coding systems will be used interchangeably.

ATC

The Anatomical Therapeutic Chemical Classification (ATC)[23] is a classification system used to categorize drugs and other pharmaceutical products. This system, developed by the World Health Organization (WHO), is designed to assign codes to drugs based on their anatomical location (where they act in the body), their therapeutic action (what treatment they provide), and their chemical composition (the active components they are made of). The ATC classification provides a standardized and globally accepted way of organizing drugs to facilitate their use in research, public health management, and medical prescribing.

The ATC system is organized into hierarchical levels, with each drug given an unique alphanumeric code. This code has five levels of detail, each of which provides more information about the drug in question. At the first level, the ATC code assigns drugs based on the anatomical location where they act, using a letter that represents an area of the body or a biological system. For example, code A is reserved for drugs that act on the digestive system and metabolism, while code C corresponds to drugs that affect the cardiovascular system.

At the second level, the code is subdivided into therapeutic groups that group drugs with similar mechanisms of action. For example, within group C, which treats the cardiovascular system, C03 refers to diuretics, which have the therapeutic function of increasing urine excretion. At the third level, the code describes the therapeutic subgroup in more detail, such as C03C, which specifies thiazide-type diuretics. At the fourth level, the specific chemical group of the drug is identified, such as C03CA for thiazide diuretics, and finally, at the fifth level, a unique code is assigned to each specific drug within that group. This last level usually includes a combination of letters and numbers, which identify the active ingredient and the brand of the drug.

This hierarchical ATC classification system not only allows for clear and consistent organization of drugs but also facilitates comparison between drugs within the same therapeutic or anatomical group, providing useful information for healthcare professionals, researchers and health authorities. Furthermore, by being linked to active ingredients and therapeutic classes, the ATC system also contributes to better management of drugs at the public policy level, promoting rational use of drugs and assisting in pharmacological surveillance.

Each drug is identified by a unique code, and this code is used in various applications, such as medical prescription, pharmaceutical billing and health statistics monitoring. In addition, the ATC system is used in pharmacological research to study the prevalence of drugs in different regions, as well as in the development of new therapies and in the evaluation of the efficacy of treatments.

RX-NORM

RxNorm[24] is a standardized nomenclature system developed by the National Institutes of Health (NIH) designed to provide an accurate and consistent representation of drugs, including active ingredients, drug products, dosage forms, and strengths. RxNorm is used to ensure that drugs are uniquely identified, facilitating interoperability between healthcare systems, drug information management, and clinical data integration.

Coding in RxNorm is structured in a hierarchical and detailed manner, with a focus on representing both the basic components of drugs and their relationships to other elements in the healthcare system. In RxNorm, drugs are represented through several types of concepts, including the following:

- Active drugs (ingredients): These represent the pharmacological substances or active ingredients of drugs. These are the chemical components responsible for the therapeutic action. Example: the active ingredient Paracetamol.
- Pharmaceutical products (clinical drugs): These concepts correspond to combinations of an active ingredient and a specific dosage form, often including the concentration of the active ingredient. For example, Paracetamol 500 mg in tablet form is a pharmaceutical product.

- Dosage forms: These reflect the form in which the drug is administered, such as tablets, capsules, injectable solutions, etc.
- Prescriptions and trademarks: RxNorm also allows drugs to be represented as trademarks or specific names used by manufacturers. For example, a drug could be linked to its generic name (Paracetamol) or to a specific trademark.

Each concept in RxNorm is associated with a unique code, a numerical identifier that allows electronic health systems to recognize and interpret the drug or active ingredient accurately. RxNorm codes are used in electronic health records to efficiently record, search and query drugs. This coding system allows both physicians and pharmacists, researchers and other healthcare professionals to easily access information about medicines, including their characteristics and properties. For example, the code for Paracetamol as a specific active ingredient may have a code such as 1134600, while a pharmaceutical product such as Paracetamol 500 mg tablets could have a different unique code, reflecting both the active substance and the dosage form.

An important feature of RxNorm is its ability to represent relationships between different concepts, allowing equivalences to be made between medicines and facilitating interoperability between healthcare systems. This includes: equivalences between generic names and brand names, relationships between products and dosage forms and relationships between medicines and their active ingredients.

RxNorm is not only useful within its own system, but also integrates with other medical coding standards, such as SNOMED CT, ICD-10, Loinc and ATC. This is achieved by using mappings between different systems, which facilitates interoperability and the transfer of information between different health systems. For example, a medicine registered in RxNorm can be linked to a code in SNOMED CT to facilitate the tracking of diagnoses and treatments in an electronic medical record.

RxNorm is constantly updated to include new drugs, active ingredients, and formulations that come to market, as well as to reflect evolving practices and regulations. In addition, it is designed to adapt to the particularities of the American health care system, but its use has expanded globally.

ICD

The International Classification of Diseases (ICD)[25] is a standardized system developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) to classify and code diseases, disorders, and health conditions. Its hierarchical structure organizes diseases into general chapters based on body systems or types of pathologies, dividing them into more specific blocks until reaching individual codes that allow precise identification of each condition. For example, in the ICD-11, a code such as BA40.0 refers to acute viral myocarditis, reflecting a minimal four-character structure that facilitates classification.

The operation of the ICD begins with the medical evaluation of a patient, in which the health professional assigns a diagnosis and translates it into an ICD code using the official manual or a digital system. This code is recorded in the patient's medical record, serving to document the case, manage medical billing, and facilitate research. In the administrative field, ICD codes are essential for the justification of treatments and procedures in health insurance, ensuring that health providers receive adequate reimbursement for their services. In addition, the data collected from the ICD are essential in public health and epidemiology, allowing governments and health agencies to monitor disease prevalence, identify trends, and make informed decisions for health policy planning.

With the transition from ICD-10 to ICD-11, which came into effect in 2022, significant improvements were introduced to make the system more accurate and adaptable to the digital age. The classification is now natively digital and better integrated with electronic health records, as well as offering more detailed coding to better reflect emerging diseases, such as antimicrobial resistance and mental health disorders. Multiple coding

pathways have also been incorporated, allowing comorbidities and complications to be recorded more accurately, facilitating more precise analysis of clinical data.

The use of the ICD is fundamental in multiple areas, from clinical practice, where it standardizes diagnoses to improve medical care, to research and data analysis, helping to understand the evolution of diseases globally. It also plays a crucial role in medical billing, ensuring that procedures are clearly documented for proper payment. In the field of public health, its application allows the monitoring of diseases, the detection of outbreaks and the formulation of effective health strategies. In short, the ICD is an indispensable tool in the health field, guaranteeing a uniform and precise classification of diseases that favors clinical, administrative and epidemiological management throughout the world.

ICD-10-CM

ICD-10 Clinical Modification (ICD-10-CM)[26] is a code classification system for diseases and medical conditions developed by the CDC's National Center for Health Statistics (NCHS) and adopted in 2015 as a modification of ICD-10 with express permission from WHO, following the established ICD structure and conventions.

This adaptation expands injury codes, adds support for ambulatory and managed care encounters, reduces the number of codes needed to represent a problem fully with combinations of symptoms and diagnosis, and has increased granularity – adding laterality and sixth- and seventh-digit classifications.

ICD-10-PCS

ICD-10 Procedure Coding System (ICD-10-PCS)[27] is a hierarchical classification system developed by the U.S. in 1995-1998 to classify procedures, such as surgeries, psychotherapy, imaging, or physical rehabilitation. Even though it was named after the WHO's ICD, it was created as a continuation of ICD-9-CM instead of an extension of ICD-10.

In Europe, ICD-10-PCS started to be used in the last decade. Specifically, in Spain, ICD-10-PCS has been used as a reference for their adaptation of ICD-10 for specialized hospital procedures since 2016. Italy and Switzerland have not adopted this system as of 2025, as they use respectively ICD-9-CM and CHOP.

CIE-10-ES

While Clasificación Internacional de Enfermedades (CIE-10)[27] is the version of ICD-10 translated to Spanish, CIE-10-ES is the Spanish modification of ICD-10 to adapt it to the Spanish clinical context. It contains two branches, CIE-10-ES Diagnósticos, which integrates ICD-10-CM, and CIE-10-ES Procedimientos, which integrates ICD-10-PCS.

It includes an alphanumeric structure more detailed than the previously used CIE-10-MC including new categories and concepts, such as laterality and gravity levels, increasing clinical precision.

It can be consulted using the eCIE-Maps, a platform developed by the Spanish Ministry of Health to facilitate searches.

ICD-10-GM

ICD-10 German Modification (ICD-10-GM)[28], previously known as ICD-10-SGB-V, is an adaptation of ICD-10 translated into German by the BfArM. It is adapted to the specific requirements of the German health care system and has been in use since 2000 to encode diagnoses in inpatient and outpatient healthcare, specially as

part of the G-DRG (German Diagnosis Related Groups). It consists of two parts, tabular list and alphabetical index. The tabular list consists of the hierarchically ordered list of codes with supplementary information of update comparisons and instructions on the encoding system. The Alphabetical index, previously known as Thesaurus of Diagnostic Terms, is a compilation of diagnoses from terminology for medical care. It has been adopted by Switzerland since 2022 for diagnostics.

SNOMED-CT

The Systematized Nomenclature of Medicine – Clinical Terms (SNOMED CT)[30] is a standardized system of medical terminology designed to represent clinical concepts in a structured and accurate manner. Unlike other classification systems, such as the ICD, which focuses on disease coding for billing and epidemiology, SNOMED CT allows for a more detailed level of clinical data representation, facilitating interoperability between health information systems.

SNOMED CT is comprised of a vast set of clinical terms organized hierarchically and structured in a relationship-based model. Each concept within SNOMED CT is represented by a unique and unambiguous identifier, ensuring that the same term can be understood in the same way across different systems and regions. For example, the concept “acute myocardial infarction” has the unique code 22298006, ensuring that any system using SNOMED CT can correctly interpret it regardless of the language or local nomenclature.

SNOMED CT codes are organized in a hierarchical and relational structure, allowing for greater accuracy in the representation of medical conditions. There are three main components to SNOMED CT:

- Concepts: Represent specific clinical entities, such as diseases, procedures, findings, or substances. Each concept has a unique numerical identifier and an associated description.
- Descriptions: Provide the terms associated with a concept. Preferred terms and synonyms exist to ensure that different ways of describing the same concept are correctly interpreted.
- Relationships: Link concepts to define their meaning within the hierarchy. For example, an acute myocardial infarction (22298006) can be related to the concept "ischemic heart disease" (414545008) as its parent category.

The operation of SNOMED CT in clinical settings allows for a richer, more granular representation of health data. When a physician records a diagnosis in an electronic health record system, rather than just typing a free term, he or she selects a SNOMED CT code corresponding to the specific diagnosis. This allows computer systems to interoperate and use this information to improve clinical decision making, medical research, and hospital management.

Unlike the ICD, which assigns a single code to each condition, SNOMED CT allows for combined, detailed coding. For example, instead of just recording “type 2 diabetes mellitus,” a SNOMED CT-based system can detail specific complications such as “type 2 diabetes mellitus with diabetic nephropathy” using relationships between multiple concepts.

Another key advantage of SNOMED CT is its adaptability to different clinical and administrative uses. It is used in electronic health records to document diagnoses, symptoms, medical history, procedures, medications, and more. In addition, it facilitates interoperability between health systems in different countries, as it allows mapping with other standards such as ICD-10, ICD-11, LOINC and RxNorm.

In practical terms, SNOMED CT is kept up to date with new editions periodically released by the International Health Terminology Standards Development Organisation (IHTSDO), ensuring that medical advances and new clinical conditions are incorporated into its database.

LOINC

LOINC (Logical Observation Identifiers Names and Codes)[31] is a coding system designed to uniquely identify clinical observations, procedures, and laboratory tests in healthcare systems. Its main objective is to standardize the communication of clinical data, facilitating the exchange of information between different systems and improving interoperability in the healthcare field. LOINC coding is organized in a detailed and structured manner, allowing for the representation of a wide variety of concepts related to clinical measurements, including laboratory tests, medical procedures, and health-related observations.

The coding structure in LOINC is based on an alphanumeric system that assigns a unique code to each concept or term. The format of this code generally consists of a series of numbers and, in some cases, letters, which allow for the precise identification of the type of observation, the method used, and other relevant characteristics. Each LOINC code is associated with a description that provides detailed information about what it represents, such as the type of test or measurement being performed.

A key aspect of LOINC is its ability to accurately code clinical observations. For example, a laboratory test such as a blood glucose measurement might have a LOINC code that refers to the amount of glucose measured in a blood sample. This code would include details about the type of sample (e.g., blood), the measurement (glucose), the unit of measurement (e.g., mg/dL), and other characteristics of the testing procedure. Through this structure, LOINC enables any healthcare system to consistently recognize information related to clinical tests and observations, regardless of the software or context in which it is used.

Coding in LOINC also distinguishes between different types of observations and areas of application. For example, LOINC has specific codes for laboratory tests (such as blood tests, urine tests, microbiological cultures) as well as non-laboratory observations such as clinical measurements (e.g. blood pressure), medical images (such as X-rays or ultrasounds), clinical diagnoses, and medical procedures. This classification allows LOINC to cover a broad spectrum of clinical data, making it a useful tool for all medical and healthcare disciplines.

In addition to basic coding of observations, LOINC also allows for associating relationships between codes and other coding standards or systems, facilitating integration with other health data frameworks. For example, LOINC maps to SNOMED CT to ensure that clinical observations are related to the diagnoses and clinical terms described by this other coding system. In this way, LOINC becomes an integral part of a broader interoperability system, facilitating the exchange of clinical data between different healthcare applications and platforms.

The hierarchical structure of LOINC codes allows for detailed and specific searches to be performed within the system. LOINC codes are organized into categories and subcategories that represent different types of observations. Each code in LOINC has an alphanumeric format that provides information about various aspects of the observation, such as the type of test, the method of measurement, and the unit used. The first group of numbers in the code refers to the main observation (e.g., a laboratory test), while additional numbers may provide additional details about the nature of the measurement (such as the type of sample or the unit of measurement).

Over time, LOINC has evolved and expanded to cover a greater number of clinical observations and procedures. As new tests or technologies emerge in the medical field, new concepts are incorporated into the LOINC system to maintain its relevance.

UCUM

Unified Code for Units Measure (UCUM)[32] is a code standard that includes all units of measures used in engineering, business and science. Its main goal is to facilitate quantities and units' communication in an unambiguous way. It provides a set of rules and a standardized format with text codes for easy computer

interpretation. It covers all measure units used in international systems (meter “m”, milliliter “mL”). It is designed for processing and reading by computers avoiding ambiguities. It could be integrated with other standards such as HL7 and FHIR. Standardized vocabularies such as LOINC use UCUM to define the laboratory test unit.

ISO

International Organization for Standardization (ISO)[33] is an organization that develops and publishes international standards covering a wide range of areas, including healthcare and health. ISO standards related to the healthcare sector are designed to ensure the quality, safety and efficiency of medical products and services, as well as to facilitate interoperability and information management in healthcare environments.

One of the most relevant standards in the medical field is ISO 9001, which sets out the requirements for quality management systems. Although it is not specifically focused on healthcare, its implementation helps healthcare organizations improve their processes and services, ensuring that quality expectations in patient care are met. ISO 13485 is the standard that specifies the requirements for a quality management system in the design and manufacture of medical devices. This standard is crucial for the medical device industry, as it ensures that manufactured products meet quality and safety standards. ISO 15189, related to medical laboratories, this standard sets out the requirements for the quality and competence of clinical laboratories. It ensures that healthcare laboratories provide accurate and reliable results. ISO/IEC 27001, related to information security management, this standard is of particular importance for the protection of sensitive health data and ensures that healthcare organizations maintain rigorous standards for the security of patients' personal information.

Furthermore, some of the ISO standards related to data interoperability and health information coding are linked to specific coding systems such as the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), ICD-10, and other standardized classification systems that are essential for the exchange of health data internationally. These standards ensure that medical information is managed consistently and efficiently, enabling communication between different health systems.

ORPHANET

Orphanet[34] maintains the Orphanet nomenclature of rare diseases (ORPHAcodes), a unique and multilingual standard and a specific terminology for rare diseases, essential in improving rare disease visibility in health and research information systems. Orphadata provides several data formats, extracted twice a year, from the Orphanet scientific knowledge base that facilitates the exploitation of various rare disease-related datasets, among them the Genes associated with rare diseases dataset.

Orphacode coding is an alphanumeric system used to assign a unique code to each rare disease or condition. The Orphacode format follows a simple but effective structure consisting of a letter followed by six digits. The word "ORPHA" precedes the code digits, providing the nomenclature ID, while the six numerical digits specifically identify the rare disease or disorder. The Orphacode coding system is organized based on the typology of rare diseases, allowing for detailed classification of conditions based on their clinical, genetic, and epidemiological characteristics. Codes are grouped into different categories covering, among others, genetic, metabolic, neurological, musculoskeletal, cardiovascular, and hematological disorders. In addition, Orphanet provides a hierarchical classification system that organizes diseases into related groups or subgroups. For example, the condition "ORPHA2013" corresponds to a specific code within a group related to inherited metabolic diseases.

In order to better define rare disorders of genetic origin, Orphanet provides information on every gene related to a rare disorder. This information includes the genetic international nomenclature, the gene typology, the

chromosomal location, the cross-mappings with other international genetic databases. Orphanet also define the relationship between genes and their related rare disorders and provide the evidence for establishing these gene-disorder relationships.

One of the key features of Orphacodes is that it is directly linked to the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), which facilitates the linkage between rare diseases and the broader diagnostic categories used worldwide. Orphacodes also links to other classification systems and databases to facilitate access and interoperability of clinical data between different health systems and research platforms.

HPO

The Human Phenotype Ontology (HPO)[35] provides a standardized vocabulary of phenotypic abnormalities encountered in human disease. Each term in the HPO describes a phenotypic abnormality, such as Atrial septal defect. The HPO is currently being developed using the medical literature, Orphanet, DECIPHER, and OMIM. HPO currently contains over 18,000 terms and over 156,000 annotations to hereditary diseases.

OMIM

Online Mendelian Inheritance in Man (OMIM)[36] is an authoritative compendium of human genes and genetic phenotypes that is freely available and updated daily. OMIM contains information on all known mendelian disorders (genetic mutations) and over 16,000 genes. OMIM focuses on the relationship between phenotype and genotype.

CHOP

Swiss Classification of Surgical Procedures (Schweizerische Operationsklassifikation or CHOP)[37] is a system to codify, analyze and bill medical procedures like surgery and other interventions done in hospitals and clinics. Their application is mandatory, and it integrates within Swiss DRG, that defines the claim system in the Swiss healthcare system.

CHOP is developed and updated yearly by the Federal Office of Statistics (FSO), with collaboration with diverse medical entities, professionals and government bodies. Their updates allow CHOP to correctly reflect the advances in medical technology and adapt the classification to the changing needs of the medical sector through a standardized process. Releases are done multilingually in all official languages in Switzerland – Italian, French and German. In practice, the German edition can be released before the others and with more support when it comes to search engines and other related tools.

is a coding system to illustrate medical services in medical care like ICD-10-PCS. It was originally based on ICD-9-CM framework, but it has evolved to meet the Swiss healthcare system's need by providing detailed, hierarchical codes that support quality assurance, billing and statistical analysis. It is updated yearly, and is published multilingually in German, Italian and French.

It follows a structure similar to ICD with an Alphabetic Index and Tabular List, with each code being between 2 and 6 alphanumeric digits. The coding is hierarchical, starting with high-level chapter code that denote a broad category starting with 'C', while subsequent, more specific levels use codes that begin with 'Z', such as 'Z00.01 - Therapeutic ultrasound of blood vessels in the head and neck' under 'C0 - Measures and interventions not otherwise classified'. In practice, after selecting the most precise code for a procedure using the Alphanumeric Index, it is important to check that the codes used are terminal in the Tabular List, as there are many nested levels with variable length and categories can be easily mistaken for procedures.

ICF

The International Classification of Functioning, Disability and Health (ICF)[38] is a system developed by the World Health Organization (WHO) to describe and code the health status and functioning of individuals in relation to their environment. Its purpose is to provide a standardized framework for the collection, classification and analysis of information on human functioning, disabilities and contextual factors that influence health. Unlike other medical classifications, such as the International Classification of Diseases (ICD), which focuses on diagnoses and diseases, the ICF emphasizes the interaction between the person and their environment, allowing for assessment not only of medical impairments, but also functional capacity and barriers that may affect participation in society.

The ICF is organized into two main parts, each with two components. Part 1: Functioning and Disability includes: (a) Body Functions and Structures, which encompass physiological, psychological, and anatomical processes related to health, and (b) Activities and Participation, which assess a person's ability to perform tasks and participate in daily life. Part 2: Contextual Factors includes: (c) Environmental Factors, which represent external influences that may facilitate or hinder a person's functioning, and (d) Personal Factors, which include individual characteristics such as age, lifestyle, or education, although the latter are not coded in the ICF due to their cultural variability.

ICF codes follow a hierarchical alphanumeric format that allows information to be organized at different levels of detail. Each code begins with a letter, which indicates the component to which it belongs: b for body functions, s for body structures, d for activities and participation, and e for environmental factors. A number of up to five digits then identifies the specific category within that component.

Coding is comprised of a hierarchical level structured into four main digits: the first digit represents a general chapter, the second and third digits specify more detailed subcategories within the chapter, and the fourth and fifth digits add further specificity when necessary. For example, code b280 refers to “pain in general,” while b2801 specifies “pain in the whole body,” and b28015 describes “pain in the upper extremities.”

In addition to the base codes, the ICF uses a system of numerical qualifiers that allow the severity or impact of a condition to be assessed on a scale of 0 to 4. These qualifiers indicate the magnitude of the limitation or the degree of facilitation that an environmental factor provides. For example, a d450.2 code would indicate a “moderate limitation in walking,” while e110+3 would indicate that medications are a considerable facilitator in a person's health.

One of the most important aspects of the ICF is its integration with other medical coding systems, such as the ICD-10. Since the ICD classifies diseases and diagnoses, and the ICF describes the functional impact of those conditions, the two classifications complement each other to provide a more complete view of a person's health status.

ICPC

The International Classification of Primary Care (ICPC)[39] is a coding system designed to organize and structure clinical information in the field of general medicine and primary care. It includes references to existing standards like SNOMED-CT and ICD. It was developed by the World Organization of Family Doctors (WONCA) with the aim of standardizing the documentation of reasons for consultation, diagnoses and medical procedures at this level of care. Its use allows for improved collection of epidemiological data, management of clinical records and planning of health services.

ICPC is structured into three main components: Reason for Encounter (RFE), which records the main reason why the patient comes to the consultation; Diagnosis/Health Problem, which identifies the medical condition

diagnosed by the health professional; and Process of Care, which includes the treatments, diagnostic tests and medical procedures performed.

The ICPC coding system is alphanumeric, consisting of a letter and two digits. The letter indicates one of 17 chapters that group health problems according to body systems or medical categories (A: general, D: digestive, R: respiratory...). The two digits determine the specific type of problem or procedure, following a structure that organizes the codes into distinct clinical groups. Numbers 01-29 correspond to symptoms and reasons for consultation, 30-49 include administrative and medical care procedures, 50-59 represent diagnostic and preventive tests, and 60-99 cover specific diagnoses and diseases (R05 represents the symptom of cough, while R81 corresponds to the diagnosis of pneumonia). This structure allows for clear and flexible classification of health problems in primary care.

ICPC is interoperable with other medical coding systems, in particular the International Classification of Diseases (ICD). There is a correspondence between ICPC and ICD-10 codes, which facilitates their integration into electronic health records and allows data communication between different levels of healthcare.

MEDDRA

The Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA)[40] is a medical classification system designed to harmonize the terminology used in the pharmaceutical industry, clinical research, and pharmacovigilance. Its purpose is to provide a standardized language to facilitate communication between regulators, pharmaceutical companies, and researchers worldwide, ensuring a uniform interpretation of medical terms related to drugs, medical devices, and adverse reactions.

MedDRA manages its codes through a five-level hierarchical structure, allowing medical terms to be organized with varying degrees of specificity. Each term within the system is associated with a unique numerical code, which serves as a unique identifier within databases and medical information systems. At the top of the hierarchy are System Organ Classes (SOCs), which represent broad medical categories such as cardiac disorders or nervous system diseases (cardiac disorders). Next, the High Level Group Terms (HLGT) group terms within a SOC with common characteristics (heart failures), followed by the High Level Terms (HLT), which offer a more specific classification within the HLGT (left ventricular failures). At the most detailed levels are the Preferred Terms (PT), which are the standardized terms used in clinical and regulatory reports (cardiac failure congestive), and the Lowest Level Terms (LLT), which include synonyms and more detailed terminological variants (chronic heart failure).

The assignment of codes in MedDRA follows a scheme in which each term is given a unique number with no inherent meaning, which avoids ambiguities in its interpretation and facilitates its use in automated systems. These codes are managed by the Maintenance and Support Services Organization (MSSO), which is responsible for updating the dictionary twice a year to reflect new terms and medical advances. In addition, it allows users to propose changes or request the inclusion of new terms through a regulated process.

MedDRA is widely used in pharmacovigilance and clinical trials, as it allows adverse drug reactions to be reported and analyzed in a standardized manner, facilitating the detection of patterns and regulatory decision-making. Agencies such as the FDA in the United States and the EMA in Europe require its use in the presentation of drug safety data, ensuring consistency in the information.

Despite being focused on pharmacovigilance, MedDRA can be integrated with other medical coding systems such as SNOMED CT, which covers broader clinical terminology, and ICD-10, which is used in the classification of diseases. There are mapping tools that allow the conversion of terms between these systems, facilitating interoperability between medical databases and regulatory platforms.

During the trial, adverse effects to medication or other treatments might occur. The principal way to encode these for proper reporting to regulatory entities for safety purposes is the Medical Dictionary for Regulatory Activities (MedDRA). In this project, this vocabulary should not need to be processed because observations of symptoms or other events that are part of this adverse effect should be able to be encoded using other preferred terminologies.

UMLS

The Unified Medical Language System (UMLS)[41] is a system developed by the National Library of Medicine (NLM) of the United States to integrate, structure and facilitate access to medical terminology used in different health information systems. Its purpose is to allow interoperability between medical databases, electronic medical records, medical terminology systems and natural language processing tools.

UMLS is not a medical classification in itself, but rather a meta-resource that groups together multiple terminologies, nomenclatures and coding systems used in medicine and biomedicine. Among the systems integrated in UMLS are SNOMED CT, ICD-10, LOINC, RxNorm, MedDRA and others, providing a common framework that facilitates conversion between these systems and unified access to medical information.

The structure of UMLS is based on three main components: the Metathesaurus, the Semantic Network and the SPECIALIST Lexicon. The Metathesaurus is the core of the system and contains millions of medical concepts drawn from various terminology sources. Each concept in the Metathesaurus is represented by a unique identifier called the Concept Unique Identifier (CUI), which allows for linking equivalent terms from different medical vocabularies.

The coding process in UMLS is managed through the CUI and other associated identifiers. Each concept can be related to multiple names and codes from different medical classification systems, allowing for their correspondence and use in different applications. In addition to the CUI, UMLS uses the Lexical Unique Identifier (LUI) to represent lexical variants of a term and the String Unique Identifier (SUI) to identify exact versions of textual strings.

The UMLS Semantic Network complements the Metathesaurus by providing a conceptual structure based on semantic categories and relationships between medical concepts. Each CUI is associated with one or more semantic categories, such as "Disease or Syndrome", "Therapeutic Procedure" or "Chemical Substance", which allows medical knowledge to be organized in a logical and understandable way.

On the other hand, the SPECIALIST Lexicon, is a resource that facilitates natural language processing in medical texts by providing grammatical rules and morphological variants of the terms present in the Metathesaurus. This allows for improved automatic information extraction and searching for medical terms in clinical databases.

In terms of interoperability, UMLS is an essential tool for the integration of medical information in clinical and research environments. It allows conversion between different coding systems, ensuring that clinical data is understandable and compatible between different health information systems.

OTHER RELEVANT TERMINOLOGIES

There is specific coding systems created for psychology. In this project, mental and behavioral data is one of the main focuses of the study. And while in the trial any occurrence of psychological disorders is an excluding criterion, past conditions do not exclude patients. Apart from ICD and SNOMED-CT, the ICD-10 branch for Mental and Behavioral Disorders (ICD-10-MBD) and the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders, Fifth Edition (DSM-5)[42] are used. In Europe, DSM-5 is very rarely used. Because of this, the use of DSM-5 will be discouraged in this project.

2.3.2.- SHIELD Terminologies

The medical terminologies that we will use in this project to standardize the data and provide semantic interoperability will be:

- **Diagnoses and conditions:** ICD-10 supplemented with SNOMED-CT and ICD-10-MBD. If the individuals responsible for conducting the trials are unable to map the local variations of ICD-10 and ICD-9 codes in their data to the standard ICD-10 and SNOMED-CT terminologies, this mapping will be attempted during data integration.
- **Medication:** ATC+DDD.
- **Units of measure:** UCUM.
- **Laboratory tests and questionnaires:** LOINC supplemented with SNOMED-CT. Should questionnaires or other tests lack an existing code in either terminology, during data integration, either custom codes will be created or a request to LOINC for the creation of new codes will be made.

For domains related to the data proposed, we will allow MedDRA for adverse effects during the clinical trial and ICD-10-PCS for procedures.

Profile	SNOMED-CT, ICD-10 (diagnoses and comorbidities), ATC (treatments)
Biophysiological	SNOMED-CT
Behavioral	SNOMED-CT, LOINC
Psychosocial	SNOMED-CT
Clinical Data	LOINC
CVD	SNOMED-CT, LOINC
Diabetes	LOINC

3. PRIVACY, ETHICS, AND LEGAL COMPLIANCE

Section 3 of the SHIELD Data Management Plan addresses the critical aspects of Privacy, Ethics, and Legal Compliance, recognizing the sensitivity of health data. The project is firmly committed to fully complying with all relevant regulations and ethical principles to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and security of participants' data. The key data management principles followed include lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality.

UNIBA

This study is designed to comply with all relevant privacy, ethical, and legal regulations, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and security of participants' data. The research will adhere to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679), which establishes strict guidelines on data processing, storage, and transfer to protect individuals' rights and personal information. Data collection will be carried out in compliance with GDPR principles, including lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality. All collected data will be pseudonymized before storage and analysis, and personal identifiers will be removed whenever possible.

The data will be securely stored in RedCap, a widely used and GDPR-compliant platform for clinical and research data management. Only authorized personnel will have access to the data, and any data transfer will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access or breaches. The study protocol will undergo ethical review and approval by the Local Ethics Committee (EC) in the IRCCS Oncologico di Bari - Istituto Tumori "Giovanni Paolo II" before the initiation of any data collection.

Informed consent will be obtained from all participants prior to data collection, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and national ethical regulations. The consent process will be clear, voluntary, and include detailed information about data use, storage duration, and participants' rights regarding data withdrawal and access.

UNIBA will also take part in the prospective data collection for the clinical study, which will include the management of data obtained from wearable devices and self-reported questionnaires collected through the SHIELD mobile application. These data will be securely stored within the SHIELD project infrastructure.

UNIGE

This study is designed to comply with all relevant privacy, ethical, and legal regulations, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and security of participants' data. The research will adhere to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679) and the "Loi sur l'information du public, l'accès aux documents et la protection des données personnelles (LIPAD)"², which establishes strict guidelines on data processing, storage, and transfer to protect individuals' rights and personal information. Data collection will be carried out in compliance with GDPR/LIPAD principles, including lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality. All collected data will be pseudonymized before storage and analysis, and personal identifiers will be removed whenever possible. The data will be securely stored in the servers dedicated from the University of Geneva. Only authorized personnel will have access to the data, and any data transfer will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access or breaches. The study protocol will undergo ethical review and approval by the Commission Cantonale d'Ethique de la Recherche sur l'être humain (CCER) before the initiation of any data collection. Informed consent will be

² <https://www.unige.ch/universite/reglements/lipad>

obtained from all participants prior to data collection, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and national ethical regulations. The consent process will be clear, voluntary, and include detailed information about data use, storage duration, and participants' rights regarding data withdrawal and access. Participants will be given a minimum of a week to reflect before the signature of the consent.

Finally, all data will be collected and stored by the mQoL-Lab system. Human subject studies usually have three constituents: two “actors” – (i) participants and (ii) researchers - and (iii) the “system” (mQoL-Lab). Fig. 1 shows the study participants on the left-hand side, and the researchers conducting the study on the right-hand side. The mQoL-Lab system with its central server role, is depicted in the middle, as it enables the data collection from participants (clients), by using artefacts such as smartphones and wearable devices, and data analysis by the researchers. For instance, in human-computer interaction, during mobile studies, the collected data pertains to the interaction between the participant and the artefacts (e.g., smartphone) in context; in behavioral science, the collected data pertains to the participant behaviors (e.g., sleep, exercise) in context, as measured by these artefacts (e.g., wearables, smartphone).

The smartphone application does not allow the user to access any of own datasets in any form (machine or human readable). The Personal Profile available via a web-based interface (hosted at the mQoL-Lab server) will not allow the user to access any raw data; only see the cumulated, daily data and trends.

Figure 1: Operational MqoL-Lab View: Overall Data Flow of a Generic Human Subjects Study with Participants (on the left) and Researchers (on the right)

SERMAS

This study has been designed in strict compliance with all applicable privacy, ethical, and legal regulations, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and security of participants’ data. The research will be conducted in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) (EU 2016/679), which sets out stringent requirements for the processing, storage, and transfer of personal data in order to safeguard individual rights and personal information.

Data collection will be carried out in alignment with the core principles of the GDPR, including lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimisation, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality. All data will be pseudonymised prior to storage and analysis, with personal identifiers removed wherever feasible.

Data will be securely stored using REDCap, a widely adopted, GDPR-compliant platform for the management of clinical and research data. Access to the data will be strictly limited to authorised personnel, and all data transfers will be encrypted to prevent unauthorised access or potential breaches.

The study protocol will be submitted for ethical review and approval by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Hospital La Paz prior to the initiation of data collection.

Informed consent will be obtained from all participants before their enrolment in the prospective study, in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and relevant national ethical standards. The consent process will be clear and voluntary, providing comprehensive information regarding data usage, storage duration, and participants' rights concerning access to, withdrawal of, or modifications to their personal data.

3.1. ANONYMIZATION AND PATIENT IDENTITY PROTECTION

This section describes existing anonymization and pseudonymization processes and any additional needs at each clinical site.

UNIGE

Anonymisation: Robust anonymization and pseudonymization processes will be implemented to mitigate reidentification risks, particularly concerning demographic and socioeconomic data.

Encryption: Data collection: HTTPS (SSL/TLS) from wearable manufacturer API to server at UNIGE that also stores the data in an internal database (Trainutri). API authorization, authentication, and refresh tokens also stored in this database and exchanged over HTTPs when needed. Authorization for data processing: SSH public key-based authorization for all researchers.

Data storage: the data are stored in the server and ACL policies control the access to them, by default they can only be read by the researcher and by the data generator. The data from one participant is totally disconnected from the other participant (no links).

Integrity monitoring: mQoL-Lab monitors the mere presence of data at maximum per-hour frequency through programs that run periodically in the same server as the data, read the data only from its location on storage (database), and store the results in the same server as well (essentially, no monitoring outside of the server). The monitoring algorithms will serve the purposes of: (1) correct and complete data collection by the mQoL-Lab server itself, (2) identification of human factors of non-participation (e.g., the participant forgets to wear the device, forgets to charge its battery, etc), (3) identification of technological factors of non-participation (e.g., the device encounters hardware or software faults), (4) contact the participant in the case their data is missing (without further assessing the “values” of the data), and (5) derivation of data quality metrics & measurement for publications.

Archiving: The data are archived on an offline hard disk for long term preservation, totally anonymized, for research reproducibly purposes on Yareta.

UNIBA

At UNIBA, the study is designed to comply with all relevant privacy, ethical, and legal regulations, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and security of participant data. The research will adhere to the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU 2016/679), which provides strict guidelines on data processing, storage, and transfer. Data collection will follow GDPR principles, and all collected data will be pseudonymized prior to storage and analysis, with personal identifiers removed whenever possible.

Anonymisation: Data collected by researchers and recorded in RedCap will be anonymized or pseudonymized in compliance with data protection regulations.

Encryption and Data Storage: Access to collected data will be strictly limited to authorized personnel, and all data transfers will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access or breaches. Robust anonymization and pseudonymization processes will be implemented to minimize reidentification risks.

UNIBA has its own ethics committee and contributes to SHIELD as a clinical site performing data collection and local data stewardship activities. Personal data processing remains under the responsibility of the corresponding Data Controller, while anonymization or pseudonymization measures are implemented at site level in accordance with the project governance framework.

SERMAS

For SERMAS, both retrospective and prospective data collection is subject to ethical approval by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Hospital Universitario La Paz and the Fundación para la Investigación Biomédica de La Paz. Participation in the Preven-HF-AI clinical trial for prospective data requires written informed consent from all enrolled patients. The study will comply with the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki, Good Clinical Practice, the GDPR (EU 2016/679), and Spanish national legislation on personal data confidentiality (Ley Orgánica 3/2018).

Anonymisation: Robust anonymization and pseudonymization processes will be implemented to mitigate reidentification risks, particularly concerning demographic and socioeconomic data.

Encryption and Data Storage: Access to collected data will be restricted to authorized personnel only, and all data transfers will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access. The SERMAS informed consent form explicitly mentions the anonymization of images and clinical information when used for educational or scientific purposes. Patient data will never leave the clinical site, as a federated learning architecture ensures data remains decentralized and securely stored within the hospitals.

Archiving: Once the interventional data collection phase concludes, identifying information will be deleted, rendering the dataset fully anonymous.

SERMAS has its own ethics committee and contributes to the project as a clinical site responsible for data collection and local data stewardship. Anonymization or pseudonymization measures are implemented at site level under the responsibility of the corresponding Data Controller and in accordance with the project governance framework.

3.2. COMPLIANCE WITH REGULATIONS

In this section, each clinical partners outline steps to comply with GDPR/local regulations.

UNIGE

The University of Geneva has set up an organization to ensure compliance with LIPAD/GDPR and ethical requirements relating to personal data, and appointed a LIPAD manager and an ethics committee. Each person in charge of processing personal data complies with the requirements defined in this context. The data protection within mQoL-Lab is managed by QoL Lab researchers, having a equal responsibility and obligations for the enforcement of privacy laws and regulations in the physical world (i.e., when interacting with mQoL-Lab hardware components), as well as in the service infrastructure (i.e. when writing a service code, analyzing the data).

Policy (management of the rules): The IT charter is described at <https://memento.unige.ch/doc/0296> .

Personnel management: The mQoL-Lab is managed by the QoL Lab researchers. All personnel have undergone obligatory training in data protection and security as well as ethics (<https://elearning.trree.org/>). Any person leaving the laboratory, is automatically disabled from accessing the infrastructure. All third parties agree to non-disclosure agreement protecting the mQoL-Lab server and data security.

UNIBA

The research is designed to comply with all relevant privacy, ethical, and legal regulations, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and security of participant data. The study adheres to the GDPR (EU 2016/679), following principles such as lawfulness, fairness, transparency, purpose limitation, data minimization, accuracy, storage limitation, integrity, and confidentiality.

UNIBA has its own ethics committee, and all study protocols undergo ethical approval. All collected data will be pseudonymized before storage and analysis, with personal identifiers removed whenever possible. Robust anonymization and pseudonymization measures will be applied to reduce the risk of reidentification. Access to data will be restricted to authorized personnel, and all data transfers will be encrypted to prevent unauthorized access or breaches.

UNIBA contributes to data collection, local data stewardship, and site-level regulatory compliance within the framework of the Data Management Plan (Task 4.2). The applicable institutional data protection supervision and legal responsibilities are ensured according to the governance framework defined in this DMP.

SERMAS

The study is designed and implemented in strict compliance with applicable ethical, legal, and privacy regulations. The research will follow the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU 2016/679) and Spanish national legislation, including Ley Orgánica 3/2018. All study procedures, including retrospective and prospective data collection, require approval from the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Hospital Universitario La Paz and the Fundación para la Investigación Biomédica de La Paz. SERMAS has its own research ethics committee. The study protocol will be submitted for local ethical approval prior to the start of the pilot study.

Participation in the prospective study Preven-HF-AI requires written informed consent from all recruited patients. The SERMAS consent form explicitly states compliance with current regulations on the processing of personal data for healthcare purposes and guarantees the anonymization of images and clinical records when used for educational or scientific purposes. Robust anonymization and pseudonymization processes are implemented to mitigate reidentification risks.

SERMAS actively contributes to data management and ethics-related tasks, including the Data Management Plan (Task 4.2) and the design of the clinical study (Task 5.2). Within the project, SERMAS acts as a clinical site responsible for data collection and local data stewardship, in accordance with the legal and governance framework defined in this DMP.

International data transfers and cross-border data access.

SHIELD is designed to minimize the need for transfers of personal data across institutions through the use of a federated data architecture, under which clinical data remain, as a general rule, under the control of the originating clinical site. Cross-border processing will therefore primarily rely on local processing, secure interoperability mechanisms, and, where applicable, the exchange of model parameters or other non-directly identifying outputs rather than raw personal data.

Where access to or transfer of personal data across borders is necessary for authorized project activities, such processing shall be assessed and documented in accordance with the applicable legal framework. In the case of Switzerland, although it is a non-EU country, it is considered to provide an adequate level of data protection for personal data transfers under the applicable European framework. Where required by the specific transfer scenario, additional safeguards and contractual arrangements will be implemented. Any such transfer or cross-border access shall remain subject to the applicable ethics approvals, access restrictions, security measures, and documented governance procedures of the project

3.3. INFORMED CONSENT AND PATIENT RIGHTS

In this section, it is explained how informed consent is obtained and managed, including legal limitations. At each clinical site, the study protocol, informed consent materials, and any relevant amendments will be submitted to the corresponding Research Ethics Committee (REC) or local ethics committee for review and approval before the start of the relevant study activities. RECs will also oversee compliance with the approved ethical framework throughout the study, in accordance with applicable national and institutional requirements

UNIGE

All participants are given a minimum of 7 days from reception of the project documentation for a proper analysis and consideration on his or her participation. After this period, the human subject (participant) volunteers for participation in the study by signing an informed consent. In addition, participants will be asked if they want to be informed of any eventual accidental finding concerning their health, after discussing it with a medical professional. The participation is entirely voluntary, and the participants have the right to withdraw from the study without restrictions and justifications at any time.

UNIBA

The informed consent process is designed to comply with all relevant privacy, ethical, and legal regulations, ensuring the confidentiality, integrity, and security of participant data. The research adheres to the GDPR (EU 2016/679), the Declaration of Helsinki, and national Italian ethical regulations.

The study protocol—developed with input from UNIBA—will be submitted for ethical review and approval by the local Ethics Committee prior to any data collection. Informed consent will be obtained from all participants before any data is collected.

The consent process will be clear and voluntary, and will include detailed information on data use, storage duration, and participants' rights concerning access, withdrawal, or modification of their personal data. Participants will receive an information sheet and will be asked to sign an informed consent form, fully informing them about the study, the use of AI, and the nature of the data being collected.

UNIBA's Principal Investigators have experience with ethically approved protocols for similar studies. Access to collected data will comply with the terms of informed consent and will be overseen by the Data Protection Officer (DPO) at each trial site. Hospital Ethics Committees will supervise compliance throughout the project.

SERMAS

The informed consent process for participants in the prospective study (Preven-HF-AI) has been designed in full compliance with the Declaration of Helsinki, Good Clinical Practice (GCP), and all applicable local, national, and international regulations, including the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, EU 2016/679) and the Spanish Ley Orgánica 3/2018. All recruited patients will provide written informed consent before participating in the study.

The study protocol, defined by SERMAS, includes ethical considerations, data protection provisions, and the informed consent form. This protocol must be reviewed and approved by the Clinical Research Ethics Committee of Hospital Universitario La Paz and the Fundación para la Investigación Biomédica de La Paz prior to launching the pilot study.

Participants will be provided with a detailed information sheet and asked to sign an informed consent form, ensuring that they are fully informed about the nature of the research, the use of AI, and the data being collected, so they can voluntarily decide whether to participate. The process will be clear and voluntary,

providing comprehensive information on data use, storage duration, and participants' rights—including the right to access, withdraw, or modify their personal data, and the right to withdraw from the study at any time.

Access to collected data will be in accordance with the informed consent provided and monitored by the Data Protection Officer (DPO) at each trial site. The hospital ethics committees will supervise compliance throughout the project.

4. DATA SECURITY AND STORAGE

This section addresses the critical aspects of data security and storage within the SHIELD project. Implementing robust security measures and a reliable storage infrastructure is essential to protect participant privacy and ensure data integrity throughout the project lifecycle. SHIELD follows a "security by design" approach, complying with relevant regulations such as the GDPR, the EU AI Act, and applicable national laws. A key component of the strategy is the use of a federated learning architecture, which keeps sensitive data within the infrastructures of the partner hospitals, avoiding raw data transfers. Only locally trained AI models are shared, thereby enhancing data confidentiality.

This section outlines the specific measures implemented to ensure data security and storage. It describes the infrastructure used for data storage and the backup strategies designed to prevent data loss. It also explains the access' control mechanisms and encryption protocols in place to guarantee that only authorized personnel can access sensitive information and that data is protected both in transit and at rest. Additionally, it covers software security practices and data traceability via audit logs. Finally, it presents the plans for monitoring, auditing, and data recovery to uphold data integrity and ensure regulatory compliance.

4.1 STORAGE INFRASTRUCTURE AND BACKUP STRATEGIES

Data will be stored in a CDM implementing OMOP over PostgreSQL. An additional layer for querying data from applications (REST services) will be implemented. Both PostgreSQL database and associated services will be deployed into docker containers and over a Virtual Server to ensure interoperability across institutions.

Figure 2: Shield Data storage model

Making data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable (FAIR) involves several tasks, including data curation, use of standard vocabularies (like those in OMOP CDM), and implementation of unique identifiers. Estimated costs include staff time for data cleaning and annotation, licensing fees for any tools used, infrastructure costs for hosting searchable metadata, and integration with FAIR-compliant repositories or catalogues. For this project, we will build tools to achieve the data "FAIRification" efforts during the project execution. These costs will be covered within the project funding and institutional resources.

A backup of the software services and database structure will be stored in a shared repository of the project consortium.

Full backups of each virtual server will be scheduled at each institution. To enable point-in-time recovery this backup should be done periodically. Backup files will be encrypted and stored redundantly in each site premises due to sensitive data stored. Restoration procedures will be regularly tested to verify that data can be recovered efficiently and accurately in the event of data corruption, system failure, or human error.

4.2 DATA ACCESS CONTROL AND ENCRYPTION PROTOCOLS

Data access within the OMOP PostgreSQL database will be tightly controlled through a role-based access control (RBAC) model implemented in querying services. This model defines specific user roles: data owner, developer, administrators, data consumer, and application; with corresponding privileges tailored to their responsibilities.

For example, analysts may have read-only access to patient-level data, while data stewards may have permissions to modify or curate metadata. PostgreSQL's native role management capabilities will be utilized to enforce these privileges at the schema, table, and row levels. This layered approach ensures that each user has the minimum access necessary to perform their job functions, minimizing risk and ensuring compliance with data governance policies[43].

To authenticate users (and application) and manage their sessions securely, the service will be integrated with Keycloak, an open-source identity and access management (IAM) platform. Keycloak provides support for modern authentication protocols such as OAuth2, OpenID Connect (OIDC), and SAML, allowing seamless integration with enterprise identity providers.

Users accessing data via web query service will authenticate through Keycloak, which will manage session lifecycles, enforce password policies, and provide features like single sign-on (SSO) and two-factor authentication (2FA). This centralized authentication system simplifies user management while enhancing security.

Data will be protected both in transit and at rest using industry-standard encryption mechanisms. All data transfers between clients and the PostgreSQL server will be secured using SSL/TLS encryption, ensuring that sensitive data cannot be intercepted during transmission.

Keycloak will also be used to manage fine-grained access policies. Role mappings within Keycloak will correspond to PostgreSQL roles or application-level permissions, ensuring consistent access control across both database and application layers.

4.3 MONITORING, AUDITING, AND RECOVERY PLANS

This section provides strategies for monitoring, auditing, and recovery in case of incidents.

Monitoring Strategy

To ensure the operational health and performance of the OMOP PostgreSQL database deployed in each clinical partner, a monitoring framework will be implemented within this service.

Key metrics such as query performance, system resource usage, table growth, and user connection activity will be tracked with monitoring tools such as the Prometheus tool `postgres_exporter`. PostgreSQL's provides its own management statements extension (i.e.: `pg_stat_statements`) which will be enabled to identify and prune long running or inefficient queries.

Additionally, system-level metrics will be collected such as CPU or disk usage of servers using well-known software —i.e. using Prometheus.

Prometheus and cAdvisor are both open-source monitoring tools that can monitor these targets. Prometheus can collect, store, and query metrics exposed by monitoring tools like cAdvisor and postgres_exporter. In this case, postgres_exporter could export data concerning the PostgreSQL database's operational health and performance, and cAdvisor could collect system-level metrics of a container.

Auditing Controls

Maintaining data integrity and traceability is a priority, particularly due to the sensitive nature of clinical and patient-related data that will be stored in OMOP. An auditing mechanism will be created using a combination of software hooks into query services. This will allow for the detailed tracking of all queries to OMOP tables. These logs will be stored in secure audit tables to support compliance with data governance and regulatory requirements like HIPAA or GDPR.

Also, ETLs in charge of storing and updating data will integrate audit tables to support compliance with data governance and regulatory requirements like HIPAA or GDPR. In this way the CDM will maintain the traceability of data from sources and different loads produced in the CDM.

Disaster Recovery and Validation

The recovery plan will include clearly documented Recovery Time Objectives (RTO) and Recovery Point Objectives (RPO) to guide response efforts in the event of a major failure. A disaster recovery checklist and protocol will be maintained, including steps for verifying backup integrity, restoring the PostgreSQL service, and validating the consistency of OMOP data post-recovery. Regular validation scripts will be run to ensure data fidelity and that referential integrity across OMOP tables remains intact. These proactive measures will minimize downtime and data loss, ensuring research continuity.

Governance and Continuous Improvement

All monitoring, auditing, and recovery activities will be subject to periodic review as part of the project's overall data governance framework. Logs and metrics will be analyzed regularly to identify trends, areas for performance tuning, and potential security issues.

5. INTEROPERABILITY, REUSABILITY, AND DATA PRESERVATION

As stated above, data management in the SHIELD project is guided by the FAIR principles: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable [1][2]. These principles aim to enhance the reusability and accessibility of research data for both humans and machines. The project’s overarching data policy is to make data “as open as possible, as closed as necessary.” FAIR practices will be implemented throughout the entire data lifecycle. We detail some related issues below.

5.1 INTEROPERABILITY

The main goal of interoperability in SHIELD is to integrate heterogeneous data from diverse sources and institutions, ensuring it is understandable and compatible across different health information systems, and enabling data flow throughout the continuum of care.

The core strategy is the implementation of a Common Data Model (CDM) to ensure semantic interoperability. This CDM will be built using established standards such as OMOP and HL7. To organize siloed and multimodal data into a unified format, a Semantic Harmonization Layer based on HL7 FHIR will be applied. Additionally, a semantic harmonization API will be developed to be compatible with both HL7 FHIR and OMOP, ensuring secure and transparent access to shared data.

To ensure consistent data representation, the semantic model will leverage standard biomedical vocabularies, including SNOMED CT and ICD. The use of common standards and vocabularies facilitates interoperability across disciplines. The CDM will also be extended to integrate additional data elements related to socioeconomic, environmental, or genetic factors.

The technical infrastructure for storing, integrating, and sharing data across institutions is managed by UPM, based on a large number of related projects and experiences. This infrastructure includes deploying the OMOP database on PostgreSQL, and associated services (e.g., REST APIs) using Docker containers and virtual servers, as well as enabling data integration and authentication through FHIR servers or APIs.

Findability of data will be supported by proper metadata usage and internal project conventions defined in this DMP. Metadata standards such as Qualified Dublin Core will be used to describe data collections and facilitate discovery and reuse. Metadata will include descriptive information (e.g., title, author, keywords) and administrative details (e.g., creation date, file type, access rights). The approach to keyword definition and metadata generation is also outlined.

5.2 REUSABILITY

Reusability is enabled by ensuring that data is both findable and accessible. Standard formats such as .csv or MySQL will be used to support data sharing. Research data and results will be well documented, with metadata playing a central role in providing detailed descriptions to support reuse.

To protect participant privacy while enabling reuse, rigorous anonymization or pseudonymization procedures will be applied prior to any analysis or data sharing. Anonymized datasets may be made available for reuse.

A data documentation and licensing plan will be established to ensure future reuse under clear terms. Anonymised datasets may be shared with external researchers via open science platforms, such as the SHIELD project repository or EOSC. Ethically approved trial summaries and datasets will be made available on EOSC, with options for partial availability—e.g., anonymized summaries via tools like AMNESIA—considered for restricted datasets.

Data may also be reused in other research projects led by SHIELD partners. Additionally, models, data structures, and algorithms developed in the project may be shared with the wider research community.

5.3 DATA PRESERVATION

Data preservation [43] is the responsibility of UPM, in coordination with the clinical partners responsible for local data storage, stewardship, and preservation at site level. Data generated throughout the project will be stored in the SHIELD project repository and on servers located at the participating hospitals and at Hi-Iberia. The Common Data Model (CDM) infrastructure (OMOP on PostgreSQL) will also serve as a storage location.

Data retention is planned for a period of five years, with the specific retention period outlined in the respective informed consent forms. Clear strategies will be defined for data retention or deletion. It should be noted that in the case of anonymous user questionnaires, once submitted, the responses cannot be deleted upon request, as they are not linkable to any personal identity.

To ensure long-term preservation, backup copies will be maintained with appropriate safeguards. Data will also be electronically archived, and in the case of UNIGE, anonymized data will be preserved on an offline hard drive for long-term storage.

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

The DMP's main objective is to establish the framework for data management throughout the SHIELD project lifecycle, in alignment with the Open Science Practices of the Horizon Europe programme and in adherence to the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable).

In this updated version of the Data Management Plan (DMP), the key elements of SHIELD's data strategy have been revised and expanded based on the current status of the project. The various data sources and types to be collected—retrospective, prospective, and public—have been identified, along with their expected formats. The relevant biomedical standards and vocabularies for harmonization and interoperability have also been established, including the implementation of a Common Data Model (CDM) based on OMOP, a FHIR-based semantic harmonization layer, and terminologies such as SNOMED CT, ICD, LOINC, ATC, MeDRA, and RxNorm.

Ethical, legal, and privacy aspects, essential in a health-related project, have been addressed by outlining compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), anonymization/pseudonymization procedures, informed consent management, and data storage and access security measures.

Interoperability is ensured through both technical and semantic standardization. Reusability is promoted through adherence to FAIR principles and the intention to share anonymized data, while preservation is planned through robust backup and retention strategies. As the lead partner in data architecture and management (WP6), UPM is responsible for defining the strategies in these areas.

6.1.- FUTURE WORK

As this is an updated version of the DMP, the next phases of the SHIELD project could still require further refinements and updates to the plan. Several aspects will be expanded and detailed further:

- Data collection and consolidation procedures, currently presented at a general level, will be refined to include site-specific protocols for clinical partners as well as data captured via the mobile application.
- Final plans for data archiving and long-term access to anonymized datasets will be defined, including the selection of appropriate FAIR-compliant repositories to ensure data availability.
- The DMP will be updated regularly to reflect the project's evolution, newly generated data, consortium decisions, and any changes in ethical or legal requirements. The final version will provide a comprehensive view of data governance across the full life cycle of the project.

6.2.- RUBRIC FOR ASSESSMENT OF THE SHIELD DMP

The methodology is based on a rubric inspired by the "Rubric for Assessment of NSF Data Management Plans." This rubric was originally developed as a key outcome of the DART project[44], with the aim of standardizing DMP reviews and ensuring the quality and completeness of proposed data management strategies.

The evaluation is structured around a set of detailed performance criteria, each typically scored on a scale from 0 to 2, reflecting the degree to which each aspect is addressed. For example: 0 – Did not address, 1 – Addressed the issue, but incomplete, 2 – Complete/detailed.

To enhance clarity and navigation, this evaluation includes direct references to the specific sections of the DMP where the relevant information can be found. This allows readers to explore in greater depth the data management strategies implemented by the SHIELD project.

Table 30: SHIELD rubric for Data Management Plan

Performance Level						
Performance Criteria				Complete/detailed	Addressed issue, but incomplete	Did not address
Types of data produced	General assessment criteria	1.1	Describes what types of data will be captured, created, or collected	The DMP describes the types of data collected from cohorts (both prospective and retrospective), including biophysiological, behavioral, psychosocial, and clinical variables. It also identifies AI-generated data and public data sources, specifying their nature (structured or unstructured) and origin. Section 2.		
	Directorate- or division-specific assessment criteria	1.2	Describes how data will be collected, captured, or created (whether new observations, results from models, reuse of other data, etc.)	The DMP outlines the data collection procedures, including the extraction of electronic medical records (both structured and unstructured), the use of tools such as RedCap, the collection of self-reported data through the mobile application, and the synchronization of data from wearable devices. It also addresses the integration of data from multiple institutions and the enrichment of datasets using public databases. Section 2.2.		

		1.3	Identifies how much data (volume) will be produced		Although the DMP mentions the number of individuals expected to participate in the pilots and the number of retrospective patients per site (based on proposal data integrated into the DMP), it does not specify the estimated data volume in terms of gigabytes, terabytes, or other storage units.	
Standards for data and metadata	General assessment criteria	2.1	Identifies metadata standards and/or metadata formats that will be used for the proposed project	DMP specifies the use of enriched metadata based on standards such as Qualified Dublin Core. It describes that the metadata will include both descriptive and administrative elements to support data discovery and reuse. Section 2.3		
		2.2	Describes data formats created or used during project	DMP mentions the use of standard data formats such as “.csv, JSON, SQL, XML” for internal exchange and potential public sharing. It describes the implementation of a Common Data Model (CDM) based on OMOP on PostgreSQL for storage, and it references terminological standards such as SNOMED CT, ICD, LOINC, ATC, MedDRA, RxNorm, CIE-10-ES, ICD-10-GM, Orphacode, ICF, ICPC for data harmonisation and standardisation. Section 2.3		

	Directorate- or division-specific assessment criteria	2.3	Identifies data formats that will be used for storing data	DMP states that data will be stored in the SHIELD project repository, on servers of the participating hospitals, and at Hiberia. Specifically, it mentions the CDM infrastructure (OMOP on PostgreSQL) as a storage location and refers to the use of standard formats for both data exchange and storage (Section 5.3).		
		2.4	If the proposed project includes the use of unusual data formats, the plan discusses the proposed solution for converting data into more accessible formats			Not defined
Policies for access and sharing	General assessment criteria	3.1	Provides details on when the data will be made publicly available		DMP states that anonymised datasets may be shared with external researchers through open science platforms. However, it does not provide a specific, clear timeline indicating when they will be made available to the general public—either after the project ends or incrementally during the project.	

	3.2 Describes how the data will be made publicly available	DMP states that anonymized datasets may be shared through open science platforms (e.g., the SHIELD project repository or EOSC). It also refers to the uploading of datasets, along with publications and public deliverables, to online repositories such as Open Research Europe and biomedical databases		
	3.3 If the data are deemed to be of a "sensitive" nature, describes what protections will be put into place to protect privacy or confidentiality of research subjects	The DMP provides an extensive discussion on the protection of sensitive data (clinical, socio-demographic, genetic). It outlines rigorous measures such as anonymization and pseudonymization, restricted access to authorized personnel, encrypted data transfers, local data storage ensuring that data does not leave the clinical sites, the use of a federated learning architecture, and the informed consent process. It ensures compliance with the GDPR and relevant national regulations (Section 2.2).		

	3.4	Describes what intellectual property rights to the data and supporting materials will be given to the public and which will be retained by project personnel (if any)		The DMP establishes the principle of "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" to balance data reuse and privacy. It states that datasets shared externally will be anonymized. Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) are managed under the consortium agreement, which distinguishes between background knowledge and foreground results. While this implies protection of proprietary data, the DMP does not explicitly detail the mechanisms in place to prevent proprietary data from being included in externally shared datasets.	
	3.5	Describes security measures that will be in place to protect the data from unauthorized access	The DMP describes security measures such as restricted access for authorized personnel, encrypted data transfers, anonymization/pseudonymization, local and federated data storage, and a storage infrastructure that includes backup strategies, monitoring, auditing, and recovery plans. It also mentions the monitoring of the integrity of the collected data (Section 4).		

Directorat e- or division- specific assessment criteria	3.6	If there are factors that limit the ability to share data, e.g. commercialization or proprietary nature of the data, plan describes those conditions and describes to whom the data will be made available and under what conditions		The DMP specifies that digital data generated will be accessible to consortium members with login credentials. Retrospective data will remain locally stored at clinical sites and will be accessible to authorized consortium members through federated learning. Anonymized datasets may be shared with external researchers via open science platforms, subject to ethical approval and the terms of informed consent. The justification for restricted access to sensitive data is based on the need to protect privacy and mitigate the risk of reidentification.	
	3.7	Describes how long the data will be retained and made available to people outside of the project		The DMP states that data will be electronically preserved, with a retention period defined by the informed consent form. Data collected through the mobile application will be retained for a planned period of five years. The final version of the DMP is expected to provide further details on data management beyond the end of the project. However, the current version does not define a general retention period for all archived data or a specific timeframe for external availability, other than the five-year period for app data and what is stipulated in the consent forms.	

		3.8 IF data are going to be submitted to supplementary materials sections of peer- reviewed journals, the plan describes this	The DMP mentions scientific publications and the uploading of datasets to repositories and biomedical databases such as PubMed, but it does not specifically mention the submission of data as supplementary materials in peer-reviewed journals.	
		3.9 Describes data types or formats that will be used for making data available	The DMP states that anonymized datasets may be shared with external researchers via open science platforms (e.g., the SHIELD project repository or EOOSC), subject to ethical approval and the terms of informed consent. This specifies the type of data that will be made publicly available (i.e., anonymized), implying that only a subset or processed version of the original data will be shared.	
Policies and provisions for re-use and	General assessment criteria	4.1 Describes the policies in place governing the use and reuse of the data	The DMP is based on the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) to enhance data reuse, and states that data/results will be made "as open as possible, as closed as necessary" for reuse. It mentions that anonymized datasets may be shared with external researchers for reuse and that data may be reused in other research projects conducted by consortium partners. However, it does not specify particular licenses or provide detailed policies governing third-party reuse.	

	4.2	Describes the policies for redistribution of the data			The DMP discusses data sharing through repositories, but it does not explicitly describe policies or guidelines regarding the redistribution of those data once they have been accessed by a third party.
	4.3	Describes policies for building off of the data, such as through the creation of derivatives			Although the DMP promotes the reuse of data, models, data structures, and algorithms, it does not specify explicit policies or permissions regarding the creation of derivative works based on the shared datasets.
	4.4	Describes methods for communicating policies or guidelines for reuse, redistribution, and creation of derivatives	The DMP states that shared datasets will be accompanied by publicly accessible metadata, which will include administrative details such as access rights, and will support data discovery and reuse. This aligns with best practices for communicating policies through metadata (Section 5.1).		
Directorate- or division-specific assessment criteria					

Plans for data archiving and preservation of access	General assessment criteria	5.1	Provides details on how the data will be archived	<p>The DMP specifies that generated data will be stored in the SHIELD project repository, on hospital servers, at Hiberia, and within the CDM infrastructure (OMOP on PostgreSQL). It provides for backup strategies to ensure long-term storage and mentions the intention to deposit anonymized datasets in FAIR-compliant repositories for long-term access. The DMP does not mention physical data, as the project is focused on digital data (Section 5.3).</p>		
	Directorate- or division-specific assessment criteria	5.2	Describes how access to the archived data will be maintained	<p>The DMP suggests that access to archived data (i.e., anonymized datasets) will be maintained through sharing on open science platforms and FAIR-compliant repositories. It mentions that metadata will facilitate discovery and reuse, which implies that access will be preserved. However, it does not describe the specific mechanisms (such as DOIs or detailed discovery interfaces) that the repositories will use to ensure long-term access, relying instead on the built-in functionalities of the chosen repositories.</p>		

		5.3 Describes plans for archiving and preserving digital data	The DMP describes both physical resources (servers at hospitals and Hi-beria) and cyber infrastructure (the SHIELD repository and the CDM implemented in PostgreSQL) for data storage and preservation. It mentions backup strategies for long-term storage and the use of FAIR-compliant repositories to support long-term access (Section 5.3).		
		5.4 Describes plans for archiving and preserving physical data			SHIELD project focuses on the collection and management of digital data (electronic health records, data from wearable devices, questionnaires, public databases). No physical data or sample collections requiring archival are mentioned.
		5.5 Identifies a timeframe for how long data will be archived		The DMP states that data will be electronically preserved for a period defined in the informed consent. Data collected through the mobile application will be retained for five years. The final version of the DMP is expected to provide a more detailed overview of data management beyond the end of the project. However, there is currently no single, clearly defined timeframe for the archiving or external access preservation of all datasets.	

		5.6 Plan discusses the types or formats of data the investigator expects to retain in their possession	The DMP specifies that digital data generated will be stored in the SHIELD project repository and made available to consortium partners. Retrospective data will be retained locally at clinical sites. It distinguishes between internally accessible data (all generated digital data) and anonymized datasets that may be shared externally. The plan also refers to the use of standard formats and the Common Data Model (CDM) for storage purposes (Section 5.3).		
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Out of a total of 26 questions (maximum score: 52 points) included in this rubric-based evaluation, a score of 34 points was obtained. Specifically, 12 questions were marked as complete, while 10 questions were rated as partially complete.

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8. ANNEXES

A) CLINICAL QUESTIONNAIRE ABOUT DATA

Subscale	Code pre	(Original) Item English	Multiple choice questionnaire
Instructions :		Please indicate the disease or condition you have :	q Cardiovascular disease (such as Heart Failure) q Type 2 diabetes
Instructions :	your health	This survey asks for your views about your health. This information will help keep track of how you feel and how well you are able to do your usual activities. Please answer every question by marking one box. If you are unsure about how to answer, please give the best answer you can.	
		1. In general would you say your health is:	Excellent Very good Good Fair Poor
		The following questions are about activities you might do during a typical day. Does your health now limit you in these activities? If so, how much? 2. Moderate activities, such as moving a table, pushing a vacuum cleaner, bowling, or playing golf	Yes, limited a lot Yes, limited a little No, not limited at all
		3. Climbing several flights of stairs	Yes, limited a lot Yes, limited a little No, not limited at all
		During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular	Yes No

		daily activities as a result of your physical health? 4. Accomplished less than you would like	
		5. Were limited in the kind of work or other activities	Yes No
		During the past 4 weeks, have you had any of the following problems with your work or other regular daily activities as a result of any emotional problems (such as feeling depressed or anxious)? 6. Accomplished less than you would like	Yes No
		7. Didn't do work or other activities as carefully as usual	Yes No
		8. During the past 4 weeks, how much did pain interfere with your normal work (including both work outside the home and housework)?	Not at all A little bit Moderately Quite a bit Extremely
		These questions are about how you feel and how things have been with you during the past week. For each question, please give the one answer that comes closest to the way you have been feeling. How much of the time during the past 4 weeks: 9. Have you felt calm and peaceful	All of the time Most of the time A good bit of the time Some of the time A little of the time None of the time
		10. Did you have a lot of energy?	All of the time Most of the time A good bit of the time Some of the time A little of the time None of the time
		11. Have you felt downhearted and blue?	All of the time Most of the time A good bit of the time Some of the time A little of the time None of the time

		12. During the <u>past 4 weeks</u>, how much of the time has your <u>physical health or emotional problems</u> interfered with your social activities (like visiting with friends, relatives, etc.)?	All of the time Most of the time Some of the time A little of the time None of the time
Instructions :	Your health behavior	Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements about your health behaviors by ticking the corresponding box. If you do not wish to answer a question, please leave the corresponding box or line blank. In the last 6 months,	Scale: 1 - Strongly disagree 2 - Disagree 3 - Neutral 4 - Agree 5 - Strongly agree
		1. I engaged in regular physical activity.	
		2. I ate a well-balanced and varied diet.	
		3. I got enough sleep to feel rested.	
		4. My weight was stable	
		5. I limited my alcohol consumption (or did not consume any)	
		6. I limited tobacco consumption (or did not consume any)	
		6. I adopted preventive behaviors (vaccinations, screening, etc.).	
		7. I used complementary or alternative medicine to improve my health (e.g. acupuncture, homeopathy, etc.).	

Instructions :		Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements about managing your diabetes. In the last 6 months,	Scale: 1 - Strongly disagree 2 - Disagree 3 - Neutral 4 - Agree 5 - Strongly agree
		1. I felt well informed about the treatment options available for diabetes.	
		2. I found it easy to manage my diet to control my diabetes.	
		3. I felt supported by healthcare professionals in managing my diabetes.	
		4. The tools I used (glucometer, mobile applications, etc.) effectively helped me monitor my blood glucose levels.	
		5. I felt confident in adjusting my insulin or medication doses according to my needs.	
		6. I took my medication or insulin and performed my blood glucose checks exactly as recommended by my doctor.	
		1. I felt well informed about the treatment options available for heart failure.	
		2. I found it easy to manage fluid balance to control my heart failure.	
		3. I feel felt supported by healthcare professionals in managing my heart failure	
		4. The tools I use used (scales, pulse oximeter, applications, etc.) effectively helped me monitor my dyspnea (Feeling short of breath)	

		5. I felt confident in adjusting my furosemide or other medication doses according to my needs.	
		6. I took my medication exactly as recommended by my doctor.	
Instructions :		<p>Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements about the impact of your disease on different aspects of your life. If you do not wish to answer a question, please leave the corresponding box or line blank.</p> <p>Please remember that disease below refers to diabetes and/or cardiovascular heart disease (as per the earlier question) In the last 6 months,</p>	<p>Scale: 1 - Strongly disagree 2 - Disagree 3 - Neutral 4 - Agree 5 - Strongly agree</p>
		1. My disease has had a negative impact on my performance at work	
		2. My disease has affected my relationship with my partner.	
		3. My disease had affected my family's equilibrium.	
		4. My disease has limited my social interactions with friends.	
		5. My disease has complicated my future plans.	
		6. My disease has caused financial difficulties.	
Instructions :		<p>Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements about the resources you have at your disposal to manage your situation or disease. If you do not wish to answer a question, please leave the corresponding box or line blank.</p>	<p>Scale: 1 - Strongly disagree 2 - Disagree 3 - Neutral 4 - Agree 5 - Strongly agree</p>

		1. I can count on my partner for support.	
		2. My family provides sufficient emotional or practical support.	
		3. My friends are available to listen and help me if needed.	
		4. I have access to a trusted healthcare professional.	
		5. I participate in a support group that helps me manage my situation.	
		6. I can access other types of resources or services adapted to my needs.	
		7. To ensure your attention, select option “agree” for this statement.	
		8. I have the financial means to meet my health-related expenses.	
		9. I have access to reliable information to understand and manage my disease.	
		10. I benefit from a work or home environment adapted to my needs.	
Subscale	Code pre	(Original) Item English	Multiple choice questionnaire
current use of new technologies	instructions	<p>Please indicate which of the following devices you use on a daily basis. Several items may be ticked.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smartphone - Tablet device - Computer - Connected watch - Connected medical device (blood pressure monitor, scale, thermometer, glucometer, glucose sensor, oximeter) 	

		Do you own a connected device? yes/no If yes, which ones:	
		Please indicate from the following list the different functionalities for which you use these different devices: - Tracking your sleep - Tracking your physical activity (number of steps, kcal, etc.) - Tracking your menstrual cycle - Medication reminder - Food monitoring - Mental well-being (relaxation, meditation, etc.) - Health data tracking (heart rate, oxygenation, blood pressure, blood sugar, etc.) - Others :	
expectations and previous experience	Instructions :	If you were to use a mobile application to help you better manage diabetes/CVD, what would be your main expectations? - Improve my overall health and prevent disease-related complications - Gain autonomy and confidence in managing my disease - Optimize monitoring of my glycemic control and dietary intake or in my water balance. - Have access to a personalized treatment plan based on my objectives - Facilitate the coordination of care with the various healthcare professionals involved in my care - Educate and raise my awareness of my disease, its treatment and the lifestyle habits I should adopt. - Other	
		Have you ever used an app to manage your disease? - If yes, what were your positive experiences with these applications? - If yes, what difficulties have you encountered with these applications?	

	instructions	How likely are you to use a health app to manage your health recommended by the following people. Circle most appropriate answer	Not likely Somewhat likely very likely
		Family doctor	
		hospital consultant	
		Nurses	
		Family member	
Instructions :	functionalities	In this section, we present the different features of a disease management application. Your task is to evaluate these features as a potential user of the application. Only one feature will be presented at a time. Then, please rate your feelings about (a) the presence and (b) the absence of that particular feature.	I like it a lot I expect it It doesn't matter It's a small problem It bothers me a lot
	a	How do you feel if this feature is present ?	
	1	Complete a logbook	
	2	Connect different bluetooth devices	
	3	Have a medication reminder	
	4	Find information about your disease	
	5	Personalize notifications	
	6	Manual addition of health data (alcohol, tobacco intake, etc.)	
	7	Access to a personalized treatment plan based on my goals	

	8	Physical activity recommendations	
	9	Add photos to the application	
	10	Physical activity monitoring	
	11	Communication with a healthcare professional	
	12	Access to a supportive community	
	13	Recommendations on treatment adherence, risk reduction and prevention	
	14	Glucose monitoring	
	15	Dyspnea monitoring	
	16	Insulin requirement calculations	
	17	Control of fluid balance and medication needs	
	18	Food diary	
	b	How do you feel if this feature is absent ?	
		Complete a logbook	
		Connect different bluetooth devices	
		Have a medication reminder	
		Find information about your disease	
		Personalize notifications	
		Manual addition of health data (alcohol, tobacco intake, etc.)	

		Access to a personalized treatment plan based on my goals	
		Physical activity recommendations	
		Add photos to the application	
		Physical activity monitoring	
		Communication with a healthcare professional	
		Access to a supportive community	
		Recommendations on treatment adherence, risk reduction and prevention	
		Glucose monitoring	
		Dyspnea monitoring	
		Insulin requirement calculations	
		Control of fluid balance and medication needs	
		Food diary	
	trust in technology	As mentioned in the previous section, we intend do develop a diabetes and cardiovascular mobile application to help you better manage your disease and help you adopt, monitor and maintain healthy lifestyle habits. In this section, we want to mesure the trust that you would have in such an app. Please indicate the extent to which you agree with the following statements about trust in technology, specifically in a future mHealth mangaging app.	Scale: 1 - Strongly disagree 2 - Disagree 3 - Neutral 4 - Agree 5 - Strongly agree
Perceived Benefits	1	Using a health managing app would improve my access to my health information.	

	2	Using a health managing app would help me become more informed.	
	3	Using a health managing app would improve my ability to manage my health.	
	4	Using a health managing app would improve the quality of healthcare.	
	5	I would manage my health more effectively using a health managing app.	
Reciprocal Benefits	1	I believe that downloading a health managing app could be mutually helpful to myself and other people.	
	2	I believe my participation in a health managing app could be advantageous to me and other people.	
Social Influence	1	People who influence my attitudes would recommend a health managing app.	
	2	People who are important to me would think positively of me using a health managing app.	
	3	People who I appreciate would encourage me to use a health managing app.	
	4	My friends would think using a health managing app is a good idea.	
Internet Privacy Concerns	1	I am concerned that the information I submit on mobile apps could be misused.	

	2	I am concerned that a person can find private information about me from mobile apps.	
	3	I am concerned about submitting information on mobile apps, because of what others might do with it.	
	4	I am concerned about submitting information on mobile apps, because it could be used in a way I did not foresee.	
Intention to adopt	1	I intend to download th app when it becomes available.	
	2	I plan to download the app when it becomes available.	
	3	I predict I will download the app when it becomes available.	
Willingness to rely on app	1	I would be willing to rely on the information and advice provided by a health managing app to keep me safe.	
	2	I would be willing to rely on a health managing app to keep me informed.	
	3	I feel I could count on the accuracy of the information and advice provided by a health managing app	
Usage Intentions	1	I intend to download/keep using the app in the future.	

	2	I plan to download/keep using the app in the future.	
Subscale	Code pre	(Original) Item English	Multiple choice questionnaire
age		What is your age?	
Gender		What is your gender?	male female other does not wish to comment
educational level		Can you indicate the level of education you have attained?	No education Primary education Secondary education Higher education (university or college) Don't know Prefer not to answer
professional status		Please indicate your current professional status (several answers possible):	Retired Working full time Working part time Unemployed Working from home Incapacity insurance Other : _____ Don't know Prefer not to answer

B) INFORMED CONSENT FOR USER-GENERATED DATA VIA THE SHIELD MOBILE APPLICATION

About the Project:

The main ambition of SHIELD project funded by Horizon Europe is to leverage multimodal data collection, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and collaboration among all actors in the healthcare system to develop risk scores and identify personalized prevention strategies to be tested and validated for two NCDs (Non Communicable Disease): cardiovascular disease (CVD) and diabetes (2 of the 5 major NCDs). Partners:

- Hi-iberia ingenieria y proyectos sl (Spain)
- Servicio madrileño de salud (Spain)
- Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (Spain)
- Consorzio per la ricerca nell' automatica e nelle telecomunicazioni C.R.A.T (Italy)
- University of Limerick (Ireland)
- Università degli Studi di Bari Aldo Moro Bari (Italy)
- Qualive srl (Italy)
- Université de Genève (Switzerland)"

Purpose of this specific research study within SHIELD:

The aim of this questionnaire is to better define your needs as a typical user of the tool we would like to develop as part of this project. In other words, a mobile application enabling patients to better manage their health and well-being, and a dashboard enabling healthcare professionals to access the data collected by the app and the patient's connected devices to ensure better monitoring.

What's involved in taking part:

As part of this research, you will first be asked to answer a questionnaire about your quality of life. This questionnaire is made up of statements, and you'll be asked to judge whether or not they correspond to you. You will then be asked brief questions about your health behaviors, disease management and repercussions. Finally, you'll answer a few questions about the use and expectations of technology in healthcare.

The online survey will take approximately 10 minutes to complete.

Assurance of Anonymity

Data is collected completely anonymously. We have no way of linking your answers to your identity. In fact, we do not record any personal data that could identify you. As a result, once your answers have been recorded, we will not be able to destroy them if you so request.

What will happen with your data?

Data will be kept and archived under the responsibility of Mrs Laetitia Gosetto (University of Geneva) for 5 years. The data may be reused for other research projects carried out by the managers listed in the box at the beginning of this document. Anonymized data may be deposited on "open science" platforms (collaborative research tools) for sharing with other researchers. As the research is carried out anonymously, no individual results will be transmitted.

Contact details

If you are interested in the results of the research, please contact Ms Gosetto at laetitia.gosetto@hug.ch.

Please indicate your consent to take part in this research to proceed:

I declare that I am willing to take part in this research and that I am freely giving specific, informed, and unambiguous consent to the university to process my personal data for the purpose of undertaking the research project entitled:

Strategic health initiative for effective disease prevention

- I declare that I have been fully briefed on the nature of this study and my role in it have been given the opportunity to ask questions before agreeing to participate.
- The nature of my participation has been explained to me and I have full knowledge of how the information collected will be used.
- I am aware that such information may also be used in future academic presentations and publications about this study.
- I fully understand that there is no obligation for me to participate in this study.
- I fully understand that I am free to withdraw my participation without having to explain or give a reason, up to a period of two weeks after the data collection is completed.
- I acknowledge that the researcher does guarantee that they will not use my name or any other information that would identify me in any outputs of the research.
- I declare that I have read and fully understand the contents of the Research Privacy Notice and I explicitly consent to my personal data being processed in line with this Research Privacy Notice.

I Consent to take part in this research

I do not consent to take part in this research

RESEARCH PRIVACY NOTICE**Introduction**

This Research Privacy Notice governs the use and storage of your personal data by the University of Geneva. The processing of this data is carried out in accordance with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) / Data Protection Acts 1988-2018 (“Data Protection Law”) and in accordance with this Research Privacy Notice.

Any personal data which you provide to the University as part of this research project will be treated with the highest standards of security and confidentiality, in accordance with Irish and European Data Protection Law. This Notice sets out details of the information that we collect, how we process it and who we share it with. It also explains your rights under data protection law in relation to our processing of your data.

1. Title and Purpose of the research project
 - 1.1 Strategic health initiative for effective disease prevention
2. Research Ethics Committee
 - 2.1 Ethical approval was granted by BASEC.
3. Identity of the Data Controller(s)
 - 3.1 The Data Controller
 - University of Geneva, Geneva, Switzerland

4. Identity and Contact Details of the Data Protection Officer of the Data Controller

4.1 You can contact the University of Geneva Data Protection Officer at pdt@unige.ch.

5. The Identity of the Principal Investigator

5.1 The Principal Investigator for this Research Project is Katarzyna Wac, University of Geneva – Faculty of Economy and Management, Katarzyna.wac@unige.ch.

6. How we will use your personal data

6.1 The University must process your personal data in order to undertake research relating to this project/study. The data will be collecting from this questionnaire. Only the data from the questionnaire that you fill out will be used. This questionnaire is to better understand the need and use of an health management app.

6.2 The personal data collected and used in this research will include: sociodemographics, type of NCD : diabetes of cardiovascular disease, quality of life, health behavior, disease management, impact of the disease, resources available, application requirements, trust in health apps.

6.3 You provide us with your personal data to enable us to undertake the research project. Participation in this research project is voluntary and participants may withdraw without giving any reason. Should you wish to withdraw, you may do so by contacting the Principal Investigator at Laetitia.gosetto@unige.ch

7. Lawful Basis for University Processing Personal Data

7.1 Data Protection Law requires that the University must have a valid legal reason to process and use your personal data. This is often called a 'lawful basis'. GDPR requires us to be explicit with you about the lawful basis upon which we rely in order to process information about you.

7.2 The University is carrying out this research in the public interest and for scientific, historical or statistical purposes. In doing so, we are relying on Article 6(1)(e) of the GDPR. Where we are processing special category or sensitive personal data, we are relying on Article 9(2)(j) of GDPR. As required under Data Protection Law, we have appropriate safeguards in place in order to protect your personal data; these are set out in the next section.

8. Protecting Your Personal Data

8.1 We have the following measures in place to help ensure we keep your personal data safe:

- All researchers at the University must adhere to University policies and procedures that tell our staff and students how to collect and use your information safely;
- Training is made available to all researchers to ensure our staff and students understand the importance of data protection and how to protect your personal data;
- The University has security arrangements and technical measures in place that ensure your information is stored safely and securely;
- All research projects involving personal data are reviewed and approved by a research ethics committee in line with University policies and procedures;
- Where a research project may involve a high risk, we first carry out a data protection impact assessment to assess risks and ensure adequate safeguards are in place;

- Where your personal data is processed for health research, we will always obtain your explicit consent in advance (in line with the Health Research Regulations 2018).

8.2 Personal data collected for this research project will be pseudonymised within immediately after collection. Data will be anonymised. Truly anonymised data is not Personal Data. Once data is anonymised for the purposes of this research project, the terms of this Privacy Notice will no longer apply.

9. Sharing Your Personal Data with Third Parties

9.2 The University will disclose your personal data to external SHIELD parties where such disclosure is necessary for the research project. These third parties are set out in the Participant Information Leaflet.

10. Transfer of personal data to Other Countries Outside the EEA.

None

11. How Long Will We Keep Your Data

11.1 All Personal Data collected for this research project will be retained for 5 years.

12. Your Rights

12.1 Depending on the lawful basis which we rely on to process your Personal Data, you may have the right to request that we:

- provide you with information as to whether we process your data and details relating to our processing, and with a copy of your personal data;
- rectify any inaccurate data we might have about you without undue delay;
- complete any incomplete information about you;
- under certain circumstances, erase your Personal Data without undue delay;
- under certain circumstances, be restricted from processing your data;
- under certain circumstances, furnish you with the Personal Data which you provided us within a structured, commonly used and machine readable format;

12.2 Requests for any of the above should be addressed by email to the Principal Investigator at Katarzyna.was@unige.ch AND the Data Protection Officer at pdt@unige.ch. Your request will be processed within 30 days of receipt. Please note, however, it may not be possible to facilitate all requests, for example, where the University is required by law to collect and process certain personal data including that personal information that is required of any research participant.

12.3 It is your responsibility to let the Principal Investigator know if your contact details change.

13. Queries, Contacts, Right of Complaint

13.1 Further information on Data Protection at the University of Geneva may be viewed at <https://www.unige.ch/donnees-personnelles/>. You can contact the Data Protection Officer at pdt@unige.ch or to the leader of the project at Katarzyna.wac@unige.ch.

13.2 You have a right to lodge a complaint with the Office of the Data Protection Commissioner (Supervisory Authority) at pdt@unige.ch. While we recommend that you raise any concerns or queries with us first at the following email address Katarzyna.wac@unige.ch.

RESEARCHER'S UNDERTAKING

The information on this consent form and the answers I have given to the participants accurately describe the project. I undertake to carry out this study in accordance with the ethical standards for research projects involving human participants, in application of the Code of Ethics for Research at the University of Geneva and the Directives concerning integrity in scientific research and the procedure to be followed in the event of a breach of integrity by the University of Geneva.

C) INTERNAL DATASET INTAKE STATUS BY SITE AND STUDY COMPONENT

This annex provides an internal operational overview of the datasets received or made available so far within SHIELD, organized by site and study component. It complements the dataset descriptions included in the main body of the DMP by summarizing the current intake status of retrospective and prospective data sources, their format, level of preparation, and any pending actions required for further processing or integration.

SOURCE DATASET SUMMARY

Table 31: Source dataset summary

SITE	DATASET / SOURCE	TYPE	DATA SOURCE	PERIOD COVERED	PATIENTS	ENCOUNTERS / RECORDS	VARIABLES	IDENTIFIABILITY	FORMAT RECEIVED	SIZE	STATUS

OMOP LOADING AND TECHNICAL STATUS

Table 32: OMOP intake and mapping summary

SITE	DATASET / SOURCE	OMOP DOMAIN(S)	TARGET OMOP TABLE(S)	SOURCE IDENTIFIERS AVAILABLE	STANDARD VOCABULARIES / CODING	MAPPING STATUS	ETL STATUS	ROWS LOADED	INSTANCES LOADED	QC / VALIDATION STATUS	NOTES